

Cambridge Centre for Proteomics Mascot Search Results

User : anja
Email : aa2030@cam.ac.uk
Search title : M291 run2 (\\prot-filesvr1\data\CORE\PARAMETERS\Mascot_search_parameters\Yagnesh\M291_Ben_Luisi_Ecoli_velos_xlink_chymo_031218.par), submitted from Daemon on CCP-PC158
MS data file : \\prot-filesvr1\data\CORE\RAW_DATA_2018_Velos\Ben_Luisi\Ben_Luisi_band3.mgf
Database 1 : cRAP FullIdentifiers (117 sequences; 38809 residues)
Database 2 : CCP Uniprot Escherichia coli
Uniprot Escherichia coli_20180613 (4324 sequences; 1357163 residues)
Timestamp : 3 Dec 2018 at 11:09:44 GMT

Protein hits	: 2::sp P02930 TOLC ECOLI	Outer membrane protein TolC OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A9P0 DLDH ECOLI	Dihydrolipoyl dehydrogenase OS=Escherichia coli
	: 1::sp cRAP022 P00766 CTRA BOVIN	Chymotrypsinogen A OS=Bos taurus PE=1 S
	: 2::sp P0CE47 EFTU1 ECOLI	Elongation factor Tu 1 OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A850 TIG ECOLI	Trigger factor OS=Escherichia coli (strain ATCC 8739)
	: 2::sp P0A6F3 GLPK ECOLI	Glycerol kinase OS=Escherichia coli (strain ATCC 8739)
	: 2::sp P0ABB4 ATPB ECOLI	ATP synthase subunit beta OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0AE06 ACRA ECOLI	Multidrug efflux pump subunit AcrA OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0ABB0 ATPA ECOLI	ATP synthase subunit alpha OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A8M0 SYN ECOLI	Asparagine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A6P9 ENO ECOLI	Enolase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
	: 2::sp P0A6M8 EFG ECOLI	Elongation factor G OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P04805 SYE ECOLI	Glutamate--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0AGG8 TLDD ECOLI	Metalloprotease TldD OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A6H5 HSLU ECOLI	ATP-dependent protease ATPase subunit H
	: 2::sp P0C8J8 GATZ ECOLI	D-tagatose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase
	: 2::sp P31224 ACRB ECOLI	Multidrug efflux pump subunit AcrB OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0AFG6 ODO2 ECOLI	Dihydrolipoyllysine-residue succinyltransferase
	: 2::sp P30845 EPTA ECOLI	Phosphoethanolamine transferase EptA OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0AG67 RS1 ECOLI	30S ribosomal protein S1 OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P00350 6PGD ECOLI	6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase, decarboxylating
	: 2::sp P08200 IDH ECOLI	Isocitrate dehydrogenase [NADP] OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P21599 KPYK2 ECOLI	Pyruvate kinase II OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A6F5 CH60 ECOLI	60 kDa chaperonin OS=Escherichia coli (strain ATCC 8739)
	: 2::sp P68767 AMPA ECOLI	Cytosol aminopeptidase OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P25553 ALDA ECOLI	Lactaldehyde dehydrogenase OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0A6E4 ASSY ECOLI	Argininosuccinate synthase OS=Escherichia coli
	: 2::sp P0AG30 RHO ECOLI	Transcription termination factor Rho OS=Escherichia coli

[2::sp|P0A7D4|PURA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P22188|MURE](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0A8L1|SYS](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P76403|YEGQ](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P76658|HLDE](#) [ECOLI](#)
[1::sp|cRAP054|P04264|K2C1](#) [HUMAN](#)
[2::sp|P0A825|GLYA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P21507|SRMB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[1::sp|cRAP087|P02769|ALBU](#) [BOVIN](#)
[2::sp|P27306|STHA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P02931|OMPF](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P21888|SYC](#) [ECOLI](#)
[1::sp|cRAP112|P00761|TRYP](#) [PIG](#)
[1::sp|cRAP039|P13645|K1C10](#) [HUMAN](#)
[2::sp|P24182|ACCC](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0AEI1|MIAB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0A6H1|CLPX](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P31979|NUOF](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P16869|FHUE](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P17445|BETB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0AC38|ASPA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P60906|SYH](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P77748|YDIJ](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P02943|LAMB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P05793|ILVC](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0AD61|KPYK1](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P31068|FLIH](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0A9J8|PHEA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P33224|AIDB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0A953|FABB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0AB89|PUR8](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P25888|RHLE](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0A817|METK](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P08722|PTV3B](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P09099|XYLB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0A9B2|G3P1](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P28912|YHHI](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P24175|MANB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P25552|GPPA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P37652|BCSB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P30863|DKGB](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P77171|YDCI](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P28305|PABC](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P0AEI4|RIMO](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P77335|HLYE](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P00963|ASNA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P63020|NFUA](#) [ECOLI](#)
[2::sp|P45420|YHCD](#) [ECOLI](#)

Adenylosuccinate synthetase OS=Escherichia coli
UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-L-alanyl-D-glutamate
Serine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli
Uncharacterized protease YegQ OS=Escherichia coli
Bifunctional protein HldE OS=Escherichia coli
Keratin, type II cytoskeletal 1 OS=Homo sapiens
Serine hydroxymethyltransferase OS=Escherichia coli
ATP-dependent RNA helicase SrmB OS=Escherichia coli
Serum albumin OS=Bos taurus GN=ALB PE=1 SV=1
Soluble pyridine nucleotide transhydrogenase
Outer membrane protein F OS=Escherichia coli
Cysteine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli
Trypsin OS=Sus scrofa PE=1 SV=1
Keratin, type I cytoskeletal 10 OS=Homo sapiens
Biotin carboxylase OS=Escherichia coli
tRNA-2-methylthio-N(6)-dimethylallyltransferase
ATP-dependent Clp protease ATP-binding domain ClpA
NADH-quinone oxidoreductase subunit F OXPHOS
FhuE receptor OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
NAD/NADP-dependent betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase
Aspartate ammonia-lyase OS=Escherichia coli
Histidine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli
Uncharacterized protein YdiJ OS=Escherichia coli
Maltoporin OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
Ketol-acid reductoisomerase (NADP(+)) OXPHOS
Pyruvate kinase I OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
Flagellar assembly protein FliH OS=Escherichia coli
P-protein OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
Putative acyl-CoA dehydrogenase AidB OS=Escherichia coli
3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase 3
Adenylosuccinate lyase OS=Escherichia coli
ATP-dependent RNA helicase RhLE OS=Escherichia coli
S-adenosylmethionine synthase OS=Escherichia coli
PTS system beta-glucoside-specific EIIB
Xylulose kinase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase H repeat-associated putative transposase
Phosphomannomutase OS=Escherichia coli
Guanosine-5'-triphosphate, 3'-diphosphate binding protein
Cyclic di-GMP-binding protein OS=Escherichia coli
2,5-diketo-D-gluconic acid reductase B
Uncharacterized HTH-type transcription factor
Aminodeoxychorismate lyase OS=Escherichia coli
Ribosomal protein S12 methylthiotransferase
Hemolysin E, chromosomal OS=Escherichia coli
Aspartate--ammonia ligase OS=Escherichia coli
Fe/S biogenesis protein NfuA OS=Escherichia coli
Uncharacterized outer membrane usher protein

1::sp cRAP008 P00722 BGAL ECOLI	Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli
2::sp P76655 YQIG ECOLI	Putative outer membrane usher protein Y
2::sp P0ABF6 CDD ECOLI	Cytidine deaminase OS=Escherichia coli
2::sp P0A6A3 ACKA ECOLI	Acetate kinase OS=Escherichia coli (str
2::sp P17115 GUTQ ECOLI	Arabinose 5-phosphate isomerase GutQ OS
2::sp P0A915 OMPW ECOLI	Outer membrane protein W OS=Escherichia
2::sp P25744 MDTG ECOLI	Multidrug resistance protein MdtG OS=Es
2::sp P77416 HYFD ECOLI	Hydrogenase-4 component D OS=Escherichi
2::sp P37909 YBGD ECOLI	Uncharacterized fimbrial-like protein Y
2::sp P08839 PT1 ECOLI	Phosphoenolpyruvate-protein phosphotran

Mascot Score Histogram

Ions score is $-10 \cdot \log(P)$, where P is the probability that the observed match is a random event. Individual ions scores > 24 indicate identity or extensive homology ($p < 0.05$). Protein scores are derived from ions scores as a non-probabilistic basis for ranking protein hits.

Peptide Summary Report

Protein Family Summary	Peptide Summary	Select Summary (protein hits)	Select Summary (unassigned)	Exp
Significance threshold $p <$				
Standard scoring MudPIT scoring				
Show pop-ups Suppress pop-ups				
Preferred taxonomy All entries . . Archaea (Archaeobacteria) . . Eukaryota (eucaryotes) Alveolata (alveolates and relatives) bony vertebrates lobe-finned fish and tetrapod clade Mammalia (mammals) Mus Mus musculus (house mouse) Rattus Other mammals (rodents) Takifugu rubripes (Japanese Pufferfish) Danio rerio (zebra fish)				

Schizosaccharomyces pombe (fission yeast) Pneumocystis carinii Other Fungi Viridiplantae
Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex Other Actinobacteria (class) Firmicutes (gram-positive bacteria)
Agrobacterium tumefaciens Campylobacter jejuni Escherichia coli Neisseria meningitidis
Species information unavailable

Error tolerant

1. [2::sp|P02930|TOLC_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 53708 **Score:** 1466 **Matches:** 83(76) **Sequences:**
Outer membrane protein TolC OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=tolC PE=1 SF=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
248	400.7531	799.4917	799.4916	0.21	2	21	0.048	1	U	L.SLLQA
591	433.7343	865.4540	865.4545	-0.58	1	38	0.0015	1	U	L.ILNTA
592	433.7345	865.4544	865.4545	-0.15	1	(37)	0.0022	1	U	L.ILNTA
851	458.7769	915.5392	915.5389	0.35	1	22	0.048	1	U	L.NIKSA
1006	474.7353	947.4561	947.4560	0.20	1	(32)	0.011	1	U	F.SLSLQ
1007	474.7354	947.4562	947.4560	0.26	1	36	0.0047	1	U	F.SLSLQ
1131	482.7405	963.4665	963.4662	0.32	1	(40)	0.0015	1	U	Y.NFVGA
1132	482.7410	963.4674	963.4662	1.28	1	46	0.00047	1	U	Y.NFVGA
1407	501.7593	1001.5041	1001.5029	1.14	2	26	0.045	1	U	L.GTLNE
1409	501.7595	1001.5045	1001.5029	1.56	2	(24)	0.065	1	U	L.GTLNE
1466	507.2682	1012.5218	1012.5229	-1.09	2	(29)	0.014	1	U	L.ILNTA
1467	507.2685	1012.5225	1012.5229	-0.44	2	33	0.0059	1	U	L.ILNTA
1675	523.7789	1045.5432	1045.5444	-1.16	2	30	0.018	1	U	L.LPQLG
1676	523.7802	1045.5459	1045.5444	1.40	2	(29)	0.025	1	U	L.LPQLG
1689	526.2736	1050.5326	1050.5345	-1.88	0	(36)	0.0051	1	U	Y.TQAQK
1690	526.2736	1050.5327	1050.5345	-1.77	0	(21)	0.17	1	U	Y.TQAQK
1691	526.2738	1050.5330	1050.5345	-1.43	0	(25)	0.06	1	U	Y.TQAQK
1692	526.2750	1050.5355	1050.5345	0.90	0	42	0.0012	1	U	Y.TQAQK
1694	526.2759	1050.5373	1050.5345	2.65	0	(28)	0.032	1	U	Y.TQAQK
1702	526.7729	1051.5312	1051.5186	12.1	0	(21)	0.11	1	U	Y.TQAQK
2202	559.3144	1116.6143	1116.6139	0.42	0	(51)	0.0001	1	U	Y.KQAVV
2203	559.3149	1116.6153	1116.6139	1.30	0	57	2.4e-05	1	U	Y.KQAVV
2586	580.3375	1158.6604	1158.6609	-0.42	0	28	0.016	1	U	Y.SVGTR
2587	580.3379	1158.6612	1158.6609	0.32	0	(25)	0.029	1	U	Y.SVGTR
2877	599.7744	1197.5343	1197.5336	0.58	1	(26)	0.037	1	U	L.SQAEN
2878	599.7753	1197.5361	1197.5336	2.12	1	28	0.025	1	U	L.SQAEN
2969	605.8428	1209.6710	1209.6717	-0.61	0	43	0.00037	1	U	F.KTDKP
2970	605.8429	1209.6712	1209.6717	-0.39	0	(38)	0.0011	1	U	F.KTDKP
2983	606.3364	1210.6583	1210.6557	2.13	0	(21)	0.061	1	U	F.KTDKP
3439	639.3333	1276.6519	1276.6523	-0.31	1	40	0.0018	1	U	Y.NAKQE
3440	639.3336	1276.6527	1276.6523	0.27	1	(37)	0.0035	1	U	Y.NAKQE
3480	642.3213	1282.6280	1282.6266	1.14	0	28	0.024	1	U	Y.SGSKT
3541	647.2900	1292.5655	1292.5667	-0.89	0	(33)	0.0062	1	U	Y.DDSNM
3542	647.2921	1292.5695	1292.5667	2.22	0	40	0.0011	1	U	Y.DDSNM
3556	647.7808	1293.5471	1293.5507	-2.78	0	(22)	0.055	1	U	Y.DDSNM
3613	651.3221	1300.6297	1300.6299	-0.13	1	34	0.0059	1	U	L.SYTQA
3614	651.3233	1300.6320	1300.6299	1.65	1	(28)	0.026	1	U	L.SYTQA
3779	661.8336	1321.6526	1321.6514	0.90	0	(23)	0.13	1	U	L.QEKAA
3780	661.8336	1321.6527	1321.6514	0.99	0	47	0.00053	1	U	L.QEKAA
3789	662.3851	1322.7557	1322.7558	-0.06	1	(36)	0.00085	1	U	F.KTDKP
3791	662.3860	1322.7574	1322.7558	1.24	1	44	0.00012	1	U	F.KTDKP
4103	690.8430	1379.6714	1379.6681	2.40	0	(58)	3.6e-05	1	U	F.NNINA

4104	690.8431	1379.6716	1379.6681	2.57	0	81	1.6e-07	1	U	F.NNINA
4106	691.3326	1380.6506	1380.6521	-1.06	0	(46)	0.00053	1	U	F.NNINA
4107	691.3345	1380.6545	1380.6521	1.77	0	(49)	0.00025	1	U	F.NNINA
4424	724.8780	1447.7414	1447.7419	-0.35	0	57	4.6e-05	1	U	L.VAITD
4425	724.8793	1447.7440	1447.7419	1.42	0	(42)	0.0012	1	U	L.VAITD
4431	725.3736	1448.7326	1448.7259	4.63	0	(45)	0.00082	1	U	L.VAITD
4432	725.3743	1448.7341	1448.7259	5.64	0	(55)	8.5e-05	1	U	L.VAITD
4581	743.3500	1484.6855	1484.6817	2.59	2	(44)	0.00084	1	U	F.SSLSQ
4582	743.3502	1484.6858	1484.6817	2.75	2	55	5.8e-05	1	U	F.SSLSQ
4603	745.8637	1489.7127	1489.7121	0.46	0	85	7.8e-08	1	U	Y.RDANG
4604	745.8644	1489.7143	1489.7121	1.52	0	(71)	2e-06	1	U	Y.RDANG
4608	746.3550	1490.6955	1490.6961	-0.37	0	(67)	4.9e-06	1	U	Y.RDANG
4609	746.3565	1490.6985	1490.6961	1.61	0	(76)	5.4e-07	1	U	Y.RDANG
4610	746.3567	1490.6988	1490.6961	1.85	0	(40)	0.002	1	U	Y.RDANG
4615	746.8505	1491.6864	1491.6801	4.21	0	(69)	2.4e-06	1	U	Y.RDANG
4797	768.8994	1535.7841	1535.7831	0.66	1	(52)	0.00016	1	U	L.TLQEK
4798	768.9000	1535.7855	1535.7831	1.54	1	(42)	0.0013	1	U	L.TLQEK
4799	768.9012	1535.7878	1535.7831	3.05	1	63	1e-05	1	U	L.TLQEK
4800	768.9014	1535.7882	1535.7831	3.30	1	(26)	0.051	1	U	L.TLQEK
4801	768.9019	1535.7892	1535.7831	3.93	1	(21)	0.16	1	U	L.TLQEK
4802	769.3942	1536.7739	1536.7671	4.41	1	(40)	0.002	1	U	L.TLQEK
4875	777.3728	1552.7310	1552.7304	0.42	0	57	4.2e-05	1	U	Y.QGGMV
4876	777.3731	1552.7317	1552.7304	0.82	0	(29)	0.029	1	U	Y.QGGMV
5173	804.9251	1607.8357	1607.8307	3.08	2	43	0.00083	1	U	L.RQITG
5174	804.9251	1607.8357	1607.8307	3.08	2	(42)	0.001	1	U	L.RQITG
5777	583.2955	1746.8646	1746.8649	-0.16	1	29	0.031	1	U	L.SNPFL
6031	916.4877	1830.9608	1830.9588	1.09	1	(90)	1.9e-08	1	U	F.NVGLV
6032	916.4900	1830.9654	1830.9588	3.62	1	102	1e-09	1	U	F.NVGLV
6100	927.9518	1853.8890	1853.8829	3.29	1	(83)	1.1e-07	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6101	927.9521	1853.8896	1853.8829	3.63	1	109	3.2e-10	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6134	935.9464	1869.8783	1869.8778	0.24	1	(38)	0.0035	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6135	935.9479	1869.8813	1869.8778	1.87	1	(88)	3.6e-08	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6136	935.9489	1869.8833	1869.8778	2.91	1	(58)	3.4e-05	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6139	935.9676	1869.9206	1869.9180	1.39	1	73	1e-06	1	U	L.ANEVT
6140	935.9695	1869.9245	1869.9180	3.48	1	(66)	4.6e-06	1	U	L.ANEVT
6148	936.4422	1870.8698	1870.8618	4.28	1	(53)	9.8e-05	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6149	936.4457	1870.8768	1870.8618	8.00	1	(38)	0.0029	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6150	936.4470	1870.8795	1870.8618	9.44	1	(39)	0.0024	1	U	Y.KQAVV
6151	936.4619	1870.9093	1870.9020	3.86	1	(35)	0.0072	1	U	L.ANEVT
6251	956.9334	1911.8523	1911.8558	-1.86	1	(28)	0.031	1	U	Y.SNGYR
6252	956.9351	1911.8556	1911.8558	-0.13	1	39	0.0022	1	U	Y.SNGYR

2. [2::sp|POA9P0|DLDH_ECOLI](#) Mass: 50942 Score: 1185 Matches: 73(67) Sequences:
Dihydrolipoyl dehydrogenase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=lpdA PE=1 S
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
435	416.1980	830.3814	830.3810	0.43	0	23	0.037	1	U	Y.TEPEV
622	435.7557	869.4968	869.4970	-0.27	0	21	0.03	1	U	L.KEVPE
988	473.2764	944.5382	944.5365	1.79	1	21	0.085	2	U	L.LVMGG
1175	486.2980	970.5814	970.5811	0.30	0	25	0.015	1	U	W.KEKVI
1253	492.2983	982.5820	982.5811	0.92	1	22	0.025	1	U	L.KEVPE

<u>1742</u>	529.7872	1057.5598	1057.5590	0.74	0	(26)	0.035	1	U	L.NVGC
<u>1743</u>	529.7873	1057.5601	1057.5590	1.08	0	32	0.01	1	U	L.NVGC
<u>2614</u>	388.2042	1161.5908	1161.5931	-1.93	0	(21)	0.2	1	U	F.IPHED
<u>2616</u>	388.2050	1161.5931	1161.5931	0.05	0	21	0.18	1	U	F.IPHED
<u>2695</u>	586.3290	1170.6435	1170.6431	0.39	1	28	0.019	1	U	L.NVGC
<u>2741</u>	589.8240	1177.6334	1177.6343	-0.75	1	49	0.00017	1	U	L.GLETV
<u>2742</u>	589.8253	1177.6360	1177.6343	1.44	1	(47)	0.00023	1	U	L.GLETV
<u>3025</u>	608.8608	1215.7071	1215.7075	-0.27	0	(35)	0.0021	1	U	M.STEIK
<u>3026</u>	608.8624	1215.7103	1215.7075	2.34	0	37	0.0012	1	U	M.STEIK
<u>3168</u>	619.3711	1236.7276	1236.7302	-2.11	0	(29)	0.0027	1	U	L.VAIGR
<u>3169</u>	619.3723	1236.7299	1236.7302	-0.24	0	(47)	4.2e-05	1	U	L.VAIGR
<u>3176</u>	619.8644	1237.7142	1237.7142	-0.03	0	(52)	2e-05	1	U	L.VAIGR
<u>3177</u>	619.8645	1237.7144	1237.7142	0.16	0	53	1.7e-05	1	U	L.VAIGR
<u>3249</u>	625.3445	1248.6744	1248.6754	-0.81	1	30	0.013	1	U	Y.FDPKV
<u>3250</u>	625.3450	1248.6755	1248.6754	0.07	1	(27)	0.027	1	U	Y.FDPKV
<u>3594</u>	650.3859	1298.7573	1298.7558	1.17	1	(61)	4.3e-06	1	U	W.KEKVI
<u>3595</u>	650.3876	1298.7607	1298.7558	3.79	1	68	8.5e-07	1	U	W.KEKVI
<u>3666</u>	436.5939	1306.7600	1306.7608	-0.68	0	34	0.0012	1	U	L.HVAKV
<u>3667</u>	436.5942	1306.7607	1306.7608	-0.10	0	(26)	0.0075	1	U	L.HVAKV
<u>4112</u>	691.8619	1381.7093	1381.7089	0.34	0	(21)	0.14	2	U	L.TEKEA
<u>4113</u>	691.8623	1381.7100	1381.7089	0.86	0	31	0.012	1	U	L.TEKEA
<u>4367</u>	718.3446	1434.6746	1434.6739	0.50	0	(52)	0.00014	1	U	L.DAGKA
<u>4368</u>	718.3448	1434.6751	1434.6739	0.85	0	78	3.3e-07	1	U	L.DAGKA
<u>4369</u>	479.2324	1434.6753	1434.6739	0.92	0	(30)	0.023	1	U	L.DAGKA
<u>4370</u>	479.2324	1434.6754	1434.6739	1.04	0	(38)	0.0038	1	U	L.DAGKA
<u>4371</u>	718.3567	1434.6988	1434.6991	-0.17	0	(40)	0.0027	1	U	L.EVEGE
<u>4372</u>	718.3583	1434.7021	1434.6991	2.13	0	(41)	0.002	1	U	L.EVEGE
<u>4374</u>	718.8492	1435.6838	1435.6831	0.51	0	(42)	0.0016	1	U	L.EVEGE
<u>4375</u>	718.8515	1435.6884	1435.6831	3.74	0	43	0.0011	1	U	L.EVEGE
<u>4495</u>	731.3560	1460.6975	1460.6970	0.35	1	(51)	0.00017	1	U	Y.HALGS
<u>4496</u>	731.3561	1460.6977	1460.6970	0.51	1	60	2.2e-05	1	U	Y.HALGS
<u>4770</u>	764.8738	1527.7331	1527.7313	1.18	1	30	0.02	1	U	L.VMGGG
<u>4909</u>	779.9169	1557.8192	1557.8151	2.63	0	60	1.7e-05	1	U	F.GEPKT
<u>4910</u>	779.9169	1557.8193	1557.8151	2.71	0	(51)	0.00013	1	U	F.GEPKT
<u>5303</u>	821.4160	1640.8175	1640.8154	1.28	2	(37)	0.0047	1	U	L.LVMGG
<u>5304</u>	821.4172	1640.8198	1640.8154	2.70	2	38	0.0037	1	U	L.LVMGG
<u>5344</u>	551.3016	1650.8829	1650.8828	0.04	1	(44)	0.00044	1	U	W.VGLTE
<u>5345</u>	551.3024	1650.8853	1650.8828	1.50	1	(28)	0.017	1	U	W.VGLTE
<u>5346</u>	551.3025	1650.8858	1650.8828	1.82	1	(38)	0.0018	1	U	W.VGLTE
<u>5347</u>	826.4509	1650.8873	1650.8828	2.72	1	(44)	0.00051	1	U	W.VGLTE
<u>5348</u>	826.4514	1650.8883	1650.8828	3.32	1	46	0.00029	1	U	W.VGLTE
<u>5374</u>	829.4615	1656.9084	1656.9087	-0.15	0	(33)	0.0065	1	U	F.DQVIP
<u>5375</u>	829.4615	1656.9084	1656.9087	-0.15	0	62	8.2e-06	1	U	F.DQVIP
<u>5376</u>	553.3104	1656.9093	1656.9087	0.35	0	(28)	0.023	1	U	F.DQVIP
<u>5377</u>	553.3105	1656.9096	1656.9087	0.58	0	(30)	0.012	1	U	F.DQVIP
<u>5379</u>	553.3116	1656.9131	1656.9087	2.68	0	(44)	0.00047	1	U	F.DQVIP
<u>5380</u>	829.4643	1656.9140	1656.9087	3.23	0	(62)	7.6e-06	1	U	F.DQVIP
<u>5504</u>	841.9648	1681.9151	1681.9151	-0.00	0	51	6.3e-05	1	U	F.DNAII
<u>5505</u>	841.9675	1681.9205	1681.9151	3.20	0	(45)	0.00029	1	U	F.DNAII
<u>5607</u>	568.9642	1703.8707	1703.8665	2.48	0	(34)	0.0093	1	U	Y.VTMEG
<u>5608</u>	568.9651	1703.8734	1703.8665	4.10	0	48	0.00032	1	U	Y.VTMEG
<u>5651</u>	574.2941	1719.8606	1719.8614	-0.47	0	(28)	0.041	1	U	Y.VTMEG
<u>5652</u>	860.9380	1719.8614	1719.8614	0.03	0	(29)	0.034	1	U	Y.VTMEG
<u>5653</u>	574.2947	1719.8624	1719.8614	0.59	0	(21)	0.19	1	U	Y.VTMEG
<u>5948</u>	897.4651	1792.9156	1792.9142	0.82	2	(39)	0.0023	1	U	F.RCADL
<u>5949</u>	897.4662	1792.9178	1792.9142	2.05	2	60	2.1e-05	1	U	F.RCADL
<u>6455</u>	996.9978	1991.9810	1991.9800	0.53	1	(48)	0.00043	1	U	F.TGANT

6456	996.9984	1991.9823	1991.9800	1.14	1	(43)	0.0012	1	U	F.TGANT
6457	665.0018	1991.9835	1991.9800	1.75	1	(37)	0.0053	1	U	F.TGANT
6458	665.0031	1991.9875	1991.9800	3.77	1	(26)	0.056	1	U	F.TGANT
6460	665.3286	1992.9640	1992.9640	-0.00	1	(29)	0.029	1	U	F.TGANT
6461	997.4901	1992.9657	1992.9640	0.83	1	(75)	7.4e-07	1	U	F.TGANT
6462	997.4929	1992.9712	1992.9640	3.59	1	80	2.4e-07	1	U	F.TGANT
6463	665.3311	1992.9715	1992.9640	3.78	1	(34)	0.011	1	U	F.TGANT
6685	708.7011	2123.0813	2123.0820	-0.31	2	(38)	0.0033	1	U	F.NLMLE
6686	708.7016	2123.0830	2123.0820	0.46	2	(26)	0.051	1	U	F.NLMLE
6708	714.0345	2139.0816	2139.0769	2.20	2	(29)	0.027	1	U	F.NLMLE
6709	714.0354	2139.0844	2139.0769	3.49	2	44	0.00079	1	U	F.NLMLE

3. [1::sp|cRAP022|P00766|CTRA_BOVIN](#) Mass: 26220 Score: 1010 Matches: 120(101) S
 Chymotrypsinogen A OS=Bos taurus PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptid
125	389.1708	776.3271	776.3276	-0.65	1	33	0.0031	1		F.HFCG
126	389.1708	776.3271	776.3276	-0.58	1	(29)	0.0073	1		F.HFCG
389	412.7288	823.4430	823.4440	-1.20	1	(26)	0.019	1	U	L.KLST
390	412.7289	823.4433	823.4440	-0.76	1	(25)	0.022	1	U	L.KLST
391	412.7292	823.4439	823.4440	-0.08	1	(53)	3.4e-05	1	U	L.KLST
392	412.7292	823.4439	823.4440	-0.01	1	(53)	3.6e-05	1	U	L.KLST
393	412.7292	823.4439	823.4440	-0.01	1	57	1.2e-05	1	U	L.KLST
394	412.7292	823.4439	823.4440	-0.01	1	(34)	0.0026	1	U	L.KLST
395	412.7293	823.4440	823.4440	0.07	1	(49)	8.8e-05	1	U	L.KLST
396	412.7294	823.4442	823.4440	0.36	1	(38)	0.0012	1	U	L.KLST
643	437.7552	873.4958	873.4960	-0.29	1	(39)	0.0018	1	U	W.TLVG
644	437.7553	873.4961	873.4960	0.13	1	46	0.00028	1	U	W.TLVG
1107	481.7475	961.4805	961.4804	0.15	0	(22)	0.13	1	U	L.VCKK
1108	481.7476	961.4807	961.4804	0.34	0	28	0.026	1	U	L.VCKK
1109	481.7481	961.4817	961.4804	1.36	0	(21)	0.16	1	U	L.VCKK
1121	482.2383	962.4620	962.4644	-2.46	0	(28)	0.022	1	U	L.VCKK
1281	494.2664	986.5182	986.5185	-0.38	1	(27)	0.024	1	U	L.VNWV
1282	494.2665	986.5185	986.5185	-0.01	1	35	0.004	1	U	L.VNWV
1298	494.7584	987.5023	987.5025	-0.20	1	(35)	0.0048	1	U	L.VNWV
1299	494.7592	987.5038	987.5025	1.30	1	(23)	0.079	1	U	L.VNWV
1398	501.2540	1000.4934	1000.4938	-0.37	0	(30)	0.012	1	U	Y.TNAN
1399	501.2542	1000.4938	1000.4938	0.05	0	(25)	0.037	1	U	Y.TNAN
1400	501.2545	1000.4944	1000.4938	0.67	0	(23)	0.069	1	U	Y.TNAN
1401	501.2547	1000.4948	1000.4938	1.09	0	(26)	0.029	1	U	Y.TNAN
1402	501.2549	1000.4952	1000.4938	1.45	0	(30)	0.013	1	U	Y.TNAN
1404	501.7428	1001.4710	1001.4778	-6.77	0	(21)	0.1	1	U	Y.TNAN
1405	501.7483	1001.4820	1001.4778	4.19	0	36	0.0039	1	U	Y.TNAN
1406	501.7585	1001.5024	1001.4778	24.6	0	(20)	0.15	1	U	Y.TNAN
1495	508.7843	1015.5540	1015.5550	-0.96	1	(36)	0.0038	1	U	L.TINN
1496	508.7843	1015.5540	1015.5550	-0.96	1	(42)	0.001	1	U	L.TINN
1497	508.7845	1015.5544	1015.5550	-0.55	1	(36)	0.0043	1	U	L.TINN
1498	508.7845	1015.5545	1015.5550	-0.47	1	(50)	0.00018	1	U	L.TINN
1499	508.7848	1015.5550	1015.5550	0.01	1	51	0.00011	1	U	L.TINN
1501	508.7853	1015.5561	1015.5550	1.09	1	(47)	0.00028	1	U	L.TINN
1502	508.7860	1015.5574	1015.5550	2.41	1	(40)	0.0013	1	U	L.TINN
1503	508.7860	1015.5575	1015.5550	2.47	1	(50)	0.00015	1	U	L.TINN
1604	515.2954	1028.5763	1028.5767	-0.43	1	(24)	0.037	1	U	Y.ARVT

1605	515.2959	1028.5772	1028.5767	0.53	1	(21)	0.075	1	U	Y.ARV
1606	515.2963	1028.5780	1028.5767	1.23	1	(25)	0.029	1	U	Y.ARV
1607	515.2966	1028.5787	1028.5767	1.95	1	38	0.0016	1	U	Y.ARV
1609	515.7864	1029.5582	1029.5607	-2.44	1	(22)	0.1	1	U	Y.ARV
1610	515.7871	1029.5597	1029.5607	-1.02	1	(28)	0.024	1	U	Y.ARV
1711	527.2927	1052.5709	1052.5689	1.92	0	23	0.039	1	U	-.CGVP
2236	561.7927	1121.5708	1121.5717	-0.83	1	(30)	0.022	1	U	W.QVSL
2237	561.7927	1121.5709	1121.5717	-0.72	1	(60)	2.2e-05	1	U	W.QVSL
2238	561.7927	1121.5709	1121.5717	-0.72	1	(24)	0.074	1	U	W.QVSL
2240	561.7930	1121.5714	1121.5717	-0.28	1	(22)	0.12	1	U	W.QVSL
2241	561.7930	1121.5715	1121.5717	-0.17	1	64	8.2e-06	1	U	W.QVSL
2242	561.7933	1121.5720	1121.5717	0.26	1	(35)	0.006	1	U	W.QVSL
2243	561.7935	1121.5724	1121.5717	0.59	1	(26)	0.056	1	U	W.QVSL
2244	561.7935	1121.5724	1121.5717	0.59	1	(21)	0.18	1	U	W.QVSL
2245	561.7935	1121.5725	1121.5717	0.70	1	(42)	0.0013	1	U	W.QVSL
2246	561.7935	1121.5725	1121.5717	0.70	1	(34)	0.0082	1	U	W.QVSL
2247	561.7935	1121.5725	1121.5717	0.70	1	(22)	0.12	1	U	W.QVSL
2249	561.7936	1121.5727	1121.5717	0.92	1	(40)	0.0018	1	U	W.QVSL
2250	561.7937	1121.5728	1121.5717	1.02	1	(28)	0.03	1	U	W.QVSL
2255	561.7940	1121.5735	1121.5717	1.58	1	(42)	0.0012	1	U	W.QVSL
2256	561.7941	1121.5736	1121.5717	1.68	1	(32)	0.013	1	U	W.QVSL
2259	561.7941	1121.5736	1121.5717	1.68	1	(32)	0.012	1	U	W.QVSL
2261	561.7941	1121.5737	1121.5717	1.79	1	(47)	0.00039	1	U	W.QVSL
2262	561.7941	1121.5737	1121.5717	1.79	1	(59)	2.5e-05	1	U	W.QVSL
2263	561.7941	1121.5737	1121.5717	1.79	1	(32)	0.012	1	U	W.QVSL
2265	561.7944	1121.5742	1121.5717	2.22	1	(52)	0.00012	1	U	W.QVSL
2267	561.7946	1121.5747	1121.5717	2.66	1	(24)	0.078	1	U	W.QVSL
2277	562.2893	1122.5639	1122.5557	7.34	1	(63)	9.5e-06	1	U	W.QVSL
2315	564.2794	1126.5443	1126.5441	0.20	1	35	0.0051	1	U	L.LSNT
2316	564.2797	1126.5448	1126.5441	0.62	1	(30)	0.014	1	U	L.LSNT
2509	575.2534	1148.4923	1148.4921	0.21	1	(31)	0.0073	1	U	F.CGGS
2510	575.2536	1148.4926	1148.4921	0.52	1	36	0.0022	1	U	F.CGGS
3027	609.3223	1216.6301	1216.6299	0.16	1	40	0.0022	1	U	Y.NSLT
3028	609.3226	1216.6307	1216.6299	0.65	1	(37)	0.0041	1	U	Y.NSLT
3637	652.2772	1302.5398	1302.5398	-0.04	0	(23)	0.032	1	U	W.GSST
3638	652.2790	1302.5435	1302.5398	2.86	0	25	0.024	1	U	W.GSST
3690	655.8619	1309.7092	1309.7064	2.13	1	33	0.0048	1	U	-.CGVP
3740	660.3426	1318.6706	1318.6728	-1.67	0	(29)	0.027	1	U	F.DQGS
3741	660.3428	1318.6710	1318.6728	-1.40	0	(38)	0.0032	1	U	F.DQGS
3742	660.3431	1318.6717	1318.6728	-0.84	0	(47)	0.00045	1	U	F.DQGS
3743	660.3435	1318.6725	1318.6728	-0.28	0	(42)	0.0012	1	U	F.DQGS
3744	660.3436	1318.6726	1318.6728	-0.19	0	(45)	0.00063	1	U	F.DQGS
3745	660.3436	1318.6727	1318.6728	-0.10	0	(56)	5.2e-05	1	U	F.DQGS
3746	440.5648	1318.6727	1318.6728	-0.09	0	(23)	0.095	1	U	F.DQGS
3751	660.3440	1318.6734	1318.6728	0.45	0	(45)	0.0007	1	U	F.DQGS
3752	440.5651	1318.6734	1318.6728	0.46	0	(22)	0.14	1	U	F.DQGS
3753	440.5652	1318.6737	1318.6728	0.62	0	(25)	0.056	1	U	F.DQGS
3755	660.3442	1318.6738	1318.6728	0.74	0	(50)	0.0002	1	U	F.DQGS
3756	660.3442	1318.6739	1318.6728	0.83	0	57	4.4e-05	1	U	F.DQGS
3757	660.3444	1318.6743	1318.6728	1.10	0	(35)	0.0061	1	U	F.DQGS
3758	440.5654	1318.6744	1318.6728	1.16	0	(24)	0.087	1	U	F.DQGS
3760	660.3445	1318.6745	1318.6728	1.28	0	(44)	0.00079	1	U	F.DQGS
3761	660.3446	1318.6746	1318.6728	1.37	0	(37)	0.0041	1	U	F.DQGS
3765	660.3473	1318.6800	1318.6728	5.45	0	(48)	0.00027	1	U	F.DQGS
3767	660.3500	1318.6854	1318.6728	9.56	0	(39)	0.0026	1	U	F.DQGS
3769	440.8937	1319.6593	1319.6568	1.86	0	(37)	0.0044	1	U	F.DQGS
3770	440.8943	1319.6610	1319.6568	3.18	0	(29)	0.024	1	U	F.DQGS

3771	660.8381	1319.6616	1319.6568	3.59	0	(46)	0.00047	1	U	F.DQGS
3839	665.8638	1329.7131	1329.7140	-0.65	2	69	2e-06	1	U	Y.NSLT
3840	665.8639	1329.7132	1329.7140	-0.56	2	(53)	8.7e-05	1	U	Y.NSLT
4355	717.3151	1432.6157	1432.6194	-2.58	2	(34)	0.0036	1	U	F.HFCG
4356	717.3170	1432.6194	1432.6194	-0.01	2	56	2.8e-05	1	U	F.HFCG
4357	717.3173	1432.6200	1432.6194	0.41	2	(26)	0.027	1	U	F.HFCG
4358	717.3176	1432.6207	1432.6194	0.92	2	(32)	0.0061	1	U	F.HFCG
5519	842.3814	1682.7483	1682.7458	1.47	0	(72)	9.4e-07	1	U	F.SQTV
5520	842.3829	1682.7513	1682.7458	3.28	0	75	4.7e-07	1	U	F.SQTV
5726	869.9576	1737.9006	1737.9009	-0.19	1	(33)	0.0081	1	U	Y.TNAN
5732	869.9582	1737.9018	1737.9009	0.51	1	(25)	0.049	1	U	Y.TNAN
5734	869.9589	1737.9033	1737.9009	1.35	1	(44)	0.00063	1	U	Y.TNAN
5736	869.9593	1737.9040	1737.9009	1.78	1	(23)	0.076	1	U	Y.TNAN
5741	580.3094	1737.9063	1737.9009	3.11	1	(24)	0.059	1	U	Y.TNAN
5742	869.9606	1737.9067	1737.9009	3.32	1	(25)	0.047	1	U	Y.TNAN
5743	869.9607	1737.9068	1737.9009	3.39	1	(39)	0.0019	1	U	Y.TNAN
5744	869.9607	1737.9069	1737.9009	3.46	1	(43)	0.00067	1	U	Y.TNAN
5746	869.9612	1737.9078	1737.9009	3.95	1	51	0.00012	1	U	Y.TNAN
5751	869.9634	1737.9122	1737.9009	6.48	1	(23)	0.074	1	U	Y.TNAN
5753	870.4544	1738.8943	1738.8849	5.36	1	(38)	0.0027	1	U	Y.TNAN
5755	870.4557	1738.8968	1738.8849	6.83	1	(36)	0.0045	1	U	Y.TNAN
5913	892.4426	1782.8706	1782.8689	0.93	0	29	0.029	1	U	L.SRIV
6091	926.5032	1850.9918	1850.9850	3.67	2	38	0.0016	1	U	Y.TNAN
6092	926.5032	1850.9918	1850.9850	3.67	2	(30)	0.01	1	U	Y.TNAN
6501	1009.9964	2017.9782	2017.9780	0.15	0	(35)	0.0072	1	U	W.VVTA
6502	1009.9982	2017.9818	2017.9780	1.90	0	57	4e-05	1	U	W.VVTA

Proteins matching a subset of these peptides:

[1::sp|cRAP023|P00767|CTRB_BOVIN](#) Mass: 26309 Score: 147 Matches: 6(6) Sequences: 6
 Chymotrypsinogen B OS=Bos taurus PE=1 SV=1

[1::sp|cRAP110|P00760|TRY1_BOVIN](#) Mass: 26453 Score: 33 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 2
 Cationic trypsin OS=Bos taurus PE=1 SV=3

4. [2::sp|P0CE47|EFTU1_ECOLI](#) Mass: 43427 Score: 773 Matches: 47(46) Sequences: 47
 Elongation factor Tu 1 OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=tufA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
985	473.2684	944.5222	944.5219	0.33	1	(49)	0.00017	1	U	F.LLPIE
986	473.2685	944.5224	944.5219	0.58	1	57	2.6e-05	1	U	F.LLPIE
1513	509.7452	1017.4758	1017.4767	-0.88	1	33	0.0072	1	U	L.KALEG
1514	509.7462	1017.4778	1017.4767	1.11	1	(29)	0.02	1	U	L.KALEG
1874	541.2711	1080.5277	1080.5274	0.29	0	(43)	0.00084	1	U	L.IHPIA
1875	541.2723	1080.5301	1080.5274	2.55	0	51	0.00016	1	U	L.IHPIA
2000	549.2700	1096.5254	1096.5223	2.80	0	(38)	0.0024	1	U	L.IHPIA
2001	549.2703	1096.5260	1096.5223	3.35	0	(33)	0.0068	1	U	L.IHPIA
3013	608.3012	1214.5879	1214.5891	-1.04	0	(27)	0.029	1	U	L.DEGRA
3014	608.3030	1214.5914	1214.5891	1.88	0	42	0.0009	1	U	L.DEGRA
3191	621.2546	1240.4947	1240.4931	1.28	0	(21)	0.044	1	U	Y.AHVDC
3192	621.2558	1240.4970	1240.4931	3.16	0	23	0.031	1	U	Y.AHVDC
3226	623.8219	1245.6292	1245.6275	1.44	1	50	0.00022	1	U	L.ELVEM
3227	623.8222	1245.6298	1245.6275	1.92	1	(36)	0.0058	1	U	L.ELVEM
3347	631.8180	1261.6214	1261.6224	-0.75	1	(33)	0.012	1	U	L.ELVEM

3348	631.8199	1261.6252	1261.6224	2.26	1	(31)	0.019	1	U	L.ELVEM
3825	664.8433	1327.6721	1327.6732	-0.83	1	(44)	0.00054	1	U	L.LDEGR
3826	664.8438	1327.6729	1327.6732	-0.18	1	(48)	0.00022	1	U	L.DEGRA
3827	664.8450	1327.6754	1327.6732	1.66	1	49	0.00019	1	U	L.DEGRA
3828	664.8453	1327.6761	1327.6732	2.22	1	45	0.00049	1	U	L.LDEGR
4073	688.3607	1374.7068	1374.7064	0.24	2	(31)	0.018	2	U	L.ELVEM
4074	688.3610	1374.7075	1374.7064	0.77	2	49	0.00026	1	U	L.ELVEM
4194	467.5717	1399.6932	1399.6918	0.95	1	44	0.00078	1	U	L.IHPIA
4195	467.5717	1399.6932	1399.6918	1.02	1	(38)	0.0027	1	U	L.IHPIA
4238	706.3843	1410.7540	1410.7507	2.35	0	29	0.016	1	U	Y.IPEPE
4398	721.3863	1440.7581	1440.7572	0.62	2	46	0.00039	1	U	L.LDEGR
4399	721.3879	1440.7612	1440.7572	2.75	2	(36)	0.0031	1	U	L.LDEGR
4475	728.8828	1455.7511	1455.7470	2.78	1	26	0.039	1	U	Y.ILSKD
4913	780.3892	1558.7639	1558.7628	0.73	0	(39)	0.0029	1	U	Y.DFPGD
4914	780.3897	1558.7649	1558.7628	1.35	0	57	4e-05	1	U	Y.DFPGD
4915	780.3910	1558.7675	1558.7628	3.07	0	(40)	0.002	1	U	Y.DFPGD
4916	780.3914	1558.7682	1558.7628	3.47	0	(39)	0.0026	1	U	Y.DFPGD
5110	797.3603	1592.7060	1592.7062	-0.10	2	(40)	0.0016	1	U	F.LNKCD
5111	797.3610	1592.7075	1592.7062	0.81	2	46	0.00037	1	U	F.LNKCD
5176	805.3589	1608.7032	1608.7011	1.32	2	(24)	0.05	1	U	F.LNKCD
5177	805.3611	1608.7077	1608.7011	4.13	2	(41)	0.00092	1	U	F.LNKCD
5329	824.9253	1647.8360	1647.8324	2.20	0	(37)	0.0047	1	U	Y.VKNMI
5330	824.9288	1647.8431	1647.8324	6.50	0	46	0.00058	1	U	Y.VKNMI
5419	832.9210	1663.8275	1663.8273	0.10	0	(35)	0.0074	1	U	Y.VKNMI
5420	832.9222	1663.8298	1663.8273	1.50	0	(41)	0.002	1	U	Y.VKNMI
5685	863.4845	1724.9544	1724.9533	0.66	2	24	0.042	1	U	F.RKLLD
5888	888.9430	1775.8714	1775.8730	-0.88	1	(23)	0.12	1	U	L.DSYIP
5889	888.9443	1775.8741	1775.8730	0.64	1	35	0.0081	1	U	L.DSYIP
6208	630.6597	1888.9572	1888.9570	0.07	2	(27)	0.051	1	U	F.LDSYI
6209	945.4868	1888.9590	1888.9570	1.02	2	(32)	0.016	1	U	F.LDSYI
6210	630.6607	1888.9603	1888.9570	1.72	2	(28)	0.04	1	U	F.LDSYI
6211	945.4885	1888.9625	1888.9570	2.89	2	33	0.012	1	U	F.LDSYI

Proteins matching the same set of peptides:

[2::sp|P0CE48|EFTU2_ECOLI](#) Mass: 43457 Score: 773 Matches: 47(46) Sequences: 1
Elongation factor Tu 2 OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=tufB PE=1 SV=1

5. [2::sp|P0A850|TIG_ECOLI](#) Mass: 48163 Score: 647 Matches: 36(29) Sequences: 1
Trigger factor OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=tig PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptid
861	459.2518	916.4891	916.4879	1.33	0	22	0.11	1	U	L.RKQQ
972	472.7613	943.5080	943.5087	-0.71	0	24	0.055	1	U	Y.GASV
973	472.7617	943.5088	943.5087	0.07	0	(21)	0.1	1	U	Y.GASV
1115	482.2123	962.4100	962.4127	-2.82	1	23	0.04	1	U	F.NELM
1116	482.2127	962.4109	962.4127	-1.86	1	(21)	0.072	1	U	F.NELM
1181	486.7377	971.4608	971.4600	0.80	2	(26)	0.026	1	U	Y.KLGE
1182	486.7379	971.4612	971.4600	1.24	2	27	0.022	1	U	Y.KLGE
2080	553.2745	1104.5344	1104.5339	0.47	0	26	0.046	1	U	Y.EDPK
2469	572.3210	1142.6275	1142.6295	-1.74	1	25	0.037	1	U	L.LGEV
2816	596.7966	1191.5787	1191.5806	-1.55	0	(29)	0.026	1	U	-.MQVS
2818	596.7994	1191.5842	1191.5806	3.07	0	31	0.018	1	U	-.MQVS
3301	628.8636	1255.7126	1255.7136	-0.76	2	55	2.6e-05	1	U	L.LLGE

3302	628.8640	1255.7135	1255.7136	-0.09	2	(48)	0.00014	1	U	L.LLGE
3376	634.8057	1267.5968	1267.5972	-0.35	1	48	0.00034	1	U	Y.EDPK
3377	634.8058	1267.5971	1267.5972	-0.05	1	(36)	0.0049	1	U	Y.EDPK
3428	638.3257	1274.6369	1274.6394	-1.96	1	(32)	0.016	1	U	F.EVYP
3429	638.3292	1274.6439	1274.6394	3.51	1	41	0.0017	1	U	F.EVYP
3920	676.8745	1351.7343	1351.7347	-0.27	0	49	0.00015	1	U	L.AKAK
3922	451.5856	1351.7349	1351.7347	0.13	0	(21)	0.077	1	U	L.AKAK
3923	676.8766	1351.7386	1351.7347	2.90	0	(41)	0.00089	1	U	L.AKAK
5713	866.3706	1730.7267	1730.7272	-0.28	1	(41)	0.00067	1	U	F.TGSV
5714	866.3740	1730.7335	1730.7272	3.66	1	41	0.00073	1	U	F.TGSV
5990	909.4861	1816.9576	1816.9570	0.32	1	46	0.00044	1	U	L.KKVE
5995	909.4895	1816.9644	1816.9570	4.08	1	(37)	0.0033	1	U	L.KKVE
6173	627.6475	1879.9207	1879.9211	-0.17	2	(24)	0.096	1	U	Y.GASV
6174	627.6486	1879.9240	1879.9211	1.59	2	35	0.0087	1	U	Y.GASV
6265	641.3221	1920.9444	1920.9429	0.80	0	(37)	0.0053	1	U	W.KEKD
6266	641.3227	1920.9462	1920.9429	1.75	0	41	0.0021	1	U	W.KEKD
6916	1180.1311	2358.2476	2358.2471	0.25	1	(44)	0.00054	1	U	F.IDAI
6917	787.0905	2358.2495	2358.2471	1.04	1	(22)	0.089	1	U	F.IDAI
6918	787.0926	2358.2559	2358.2471	3.76	1	(23)	0.064	1	U	F.IDAI
6919	1180.1361	2358.2577	2358.2471	4.49	1	48	0.00017	1	U	F.IDAI
7140	873.1013	2616.2820	2616.2728	3.50	1	(63)	1.1e-05	1	U	L.EAIE
7141	1309.1487	2616.2828	2616.2728	3.83	1	(62)	1.4e-05	1	U	L.EAIE
7142	1309.1492	2616.2838	2616.2728	4.20	1	(65)	6.4e-06	1	U	L.EAIE
7143	873.1021	2616.2845	2616.2728	4.47	1	67	4.9e-06	1	U	L.EAIE

6. [2::sp|POA6F3|GLPK_ECOLI](#) Mass: 56480 Score: 605 Matches: 35(30) Sequences:
 Glycerol kinase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=glpK PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
15	380.7187	759.4229	759.4239	-1.32	0	(28)	0.019	1	U	Y.IRSNT
16	380.7190	759.4235	759.4239	-0.53	0	29	0.015	1	U	Y.IRSNT
270	402.2370	802.4594	802.4589	0.67	1	33	0.0058	1	U	Y.VVPAF
271	402.2373	802.4601	802.4589	1.52	1	(31)	0.011	1	U	Y.VVPAF
580	432.2074	862.4002	862.4007	-0.54	0	29	0.016	1	U	F.MAGAS
581	432.2076	862.4007	862.4007	0.02	0	(25)	0.052	1	U	F.MAGAS
1358	498.2442	994.4738	994.4720	1.90	1	30	0.018	1	U	L.KRDGL
1359	498.2445	994.4745	994.4720	2.59	1	(29)	0.024	1	U	L.KRDGL
2200	559.2889	1116.5632	1116.5604	2.53	0	22	0.11	1	U	F.EQIYP
2213	560.2825	1118.5504	1118.5469	3.14	0	24	0.072	1	U	L.RVDGG
2797	595.7952	1189.5758	1189.5761	-0.26	0	(42)	0.0013	1	U	L.EAMQA
2798	595.7959	1189.5772	1189.5761	0.97	0	45	0.00074	1	U	L.EAMQA
2808	596.3242	1190.6338	1190.6336	0.16	2	23	0.077	1	U	Y.VVPAF
2841	597.8099	1193.6052	1193.6040	0.97	0	55	6.1e-05	1	U	F.ATKVQ
2842	597.8102	1193.6059	1193.6040	1.57	0	(48)	0.00028	1	U	F.ATKVQ
2848	598.3046	1194.5947	1194.5881	5.57	0	(27)	0.037	1	U	F.ATKVQ
2933	603.7929	1205.5713	1205.5710	0.21	0	(31)	0.018	1	U	L.EAMQA
2934	603.7942	1205.5738	1205.5710	2.33	0	(37)	0.0041	1	U	L.EAMQA
3447	640.2977	1278.5808	1278.5802	0.46	2	(29)	0.022	1	U	L.DWDDK
3448	640.2981	1278.5816	1278.5802	1.13	2	30	0.018	1	U	L.DWDDK
3861	668.3376	1334.6606	1334.6579	2.08	0	(20)	0.22	1	U	F.RPGIE
3862	668.3380	1334.6615	1334.6579	2.71	0	32	0.016	1	U	F.RPGIE
3900	674.3676	1346.7205	1346.7194	0.85	1	39	0.002	1	U	Y.IRSNT
3901	674.3688	1346.7231	1346.7194	2.76	1	(35)	0.0055	1	U	Y.IRSNT

4110	691.8166	1381.6187	1381.6184	0.26	0	(50)	0.00015	1	U	L.TTIAC
4111	691.8184	1381.6222	1381.6184	2.73	0	63	8.2e-06	1	U	L.TTIAC
5166	803.9083	1605.8021	1605.8032	-0.68	1	30	0.029	1	U	L.MNTGE
5167	803.9095	1605.8044	1605.8032	0.76	1	(26)	0.063	1	U	L.MNTGE
6367	654.3371	1959.9895	1959.9901	-0.33	2	(44)	0.001	1	U	W.QNLDE
6368	654.3373	1959.9902	1959.9901	0.03	2	(52)	0.00017	1	U	W.QNLDE
6369	981.0031	1959.9917	1959.9901	0.79	2	56	7.1e-05	1	U	W.QNLDE
6370	981.0060	1959.9974	1959.9901	3.71	2	(52)	0.00016	1	U	W.QNLDE
7056	827.4465	2479.3178	2479.3143	1.40	0	49	0.00012	1	U	Y.GQTNI
7057	827.4482	2479.3229	2479.3143	3.47	0	(49)	0.00012	1	U	Y.GQTNI
7150	876.4714	2626.3923	2626.3827	3.64	1	23	0.051	1	U	Y.GQTNI

7. [2::sp|P0ABB4|ATPB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 50351 Score: 582 Matches: 30(27) Sequences:
 ATP synthase subunit beta OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=atpD PE=1 SV=
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
436	416.2031	830.3916	830.3923	-0.78	0	(21)	0.062	1	U	L.VVGQE
437	416.2035	830.3924	830.3923	0.19	0	22	0.051	1	U	L.VVGQE
1055	478.7740	955.5335	955.5338	-0.31	1	37	0.0014	1	U	L.VLEVQ
1056	478.7753	955.5360	955.5338	2.24	1	(25)	0.023	1	U	L.VLEVQ
1102	481.2637	960.5129	960.5128	0.14	1	(24)	0.068	1	U	Y.TLAGT
1103	481.2642	960.5139	960.5128	1.16	1	24	0.062	1	U	Y.TLAGT
1464	507.2523	1012.4901	1012.4899	0.22	1	(35)	0.004	1	U	L.TGLTM
1465	507.2525	1012.4904	1012.4899	0.51	1	36	0.0028	1	U	L.TGLTM
1833	537.8057	1073.5968	1073.5968	-0.06	2	37	0.003	1	U	Y.TLAGT
2033	550.8316	1099.6486	1099.6489	-0.20	1	25	0.023	1	U	L.LETGI
2210	560.2590	1118.5035	1118.5033	0.22	1	30	0.014	1	U	Y.DHLPE
2375	568.3265	1134.6384	1134.6397	-1.15	1	(20)	0.076	1	U	Y.VSLKD
2376	568.3268	1134.6390	1134.6397	-0.62	1	33	0.0045	1	U	Y.VSLKD
3354	633.2820	1264.5494	1264.5493	0.11	1	(39)	0.0014	1	U	L.GMDEL
3355	633.2823	1264.5501	1264.5493	0.69	1	39	0.0014	1	U	L.GMDEL
3963	679.3406	1356.6666	1356.6633	2.42	1	(37)	0.0034	1	U	Y.DALEV
3964	679.3414	1356.6683	1356.6633	3.67	1	55	4.4e-05	1	U	Y.DALEV
4099	690.3377	1378.6609	1378.6585	1.73	0	(38)	0.0033	1	U	F.GGAGV
4157	698.3339	1394.6533	1394.6534	-0.08	0	56	6.1e-05	1	U	F.GGAGV
4158	698.3344	1394.6543	1394.6534	0.62	0	(53)	0.00012	1	U	F.GGAGV
4859	773.8682	1545.7218	1545.7199	1.21	1	(26)	0.044	1	U	Y.VPADD
4860	773.8702	1545.7258	1545.7199	3.83	1	29	0.024	1	U	Y.VPADD
5011	785.4155	1568.8165	1568.8158	0.44	2	(46)	0.00035	1	U	Y.DALEV
5012	785.4173	1568.8200	1568.8158	2.70	2	(53)	7.4e-05	1	U	Y.DALEV
5015	785.9088	1569.8029	1569.7998	1.99	2	(48)	0.00028	1	U	Y.DALEV
5016	785.9088	1569.8031	1569.7998	2.07	2	57	3.4e-05	1	U	Y.DALEV
5715	866.4501	1730.8857	1730.8839	1.04	1	(45)	0.00066	1	U	L.GIYPA
5716	866.4504	1730.8862	1730.8839	1.33	1	64	8.8e-06	1	U	L.GIYPA
6363	654.0292	1959.0657	1959.0677	-1.02	1	(34)	0.0054	1	U	L.DVKDL
6364	654.0301	1959.0684	1959.0677	0.38	1	39	0.0013	1	U	L.DVKDL

8. [2::sp|P0AE06|ACRA_ECOLI](#) Mass: 42228 Score: 520 Matches: 36(33) Sequences:
 Multidrug efflux pump subunit AcrA OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=acrA
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptid
739	450.2876	898.5606	898.5600	0.69	2	20	0.033	1	U	F.LRLK
755	451.2401	900.4657	900.4665	-0.92	0	23	0.051	1	U	L.VQNG
1197	487.2691	972.5236	972.5240	-0.41	1	(36)	0.0037	1	U	L.KQEL
1198	487.2696	972.5247	972.5240	0.72	1	43	0.00086	1	U	L.KQEL
1211	487.7618	973.5091	973.5080	1.16	1	(24)	0.074	1	U	L.KQEL
1212	487.7622	973.5098	973.5080	1.86	1	(38)	0.0029	1	U	L.KQEL
2184	557.8328	1113.6510	1113.6506	0.33	0	(37)	0.0017	1	U	L.KAGD
2185	557.8335	1113.6524	1113.6506	1.66	0	39	0.00098	1	U	L.KAGD
3203	621.8624	1241.7103	1241.7092	0.93	2	(27)	0.019	1	U	L.RLKQ
3204	621.8636	1241.7126	1241.7092	2.80	2	35	0.0029	1	U	L.RLKQ
3210	622.3552	1242.6958	1242.6932	2.10	2	(20)	0.1	1	U	L.RLKQ
4020	684.3381	1366.6616	1366.6616	-0.01	1	(24)	0.078	1	U	F.KEGS
4021	684.3381	1366.6617	1366.6616	0.07	1	(30)	0.023	1	U	F.KEGS
4022	684.3384	1366.6622	1366.6616	0.44	1	49	0.00028	1	U	F.KEGS
4023	684.3395	1366.6645	1366.6616	2.14	1	(29)	0.023	1	U	F.KEGS
4024	684.3397	1366.6648	1366.6616	2.31	1	(38)	0.0032	1	U	F.KEGS
4025	684.3401	1366.6656	1366.6616	2.94	1	(48)	0.00034	1	U	F.KEGS
4376	718.8726	1435.7306	1435.7307	-0.09	0	50	0.00022	1	U	L.QITT
4377	718.8741	1435.7337	1435.7307	2.12	0	(36)	0.0057	1	U	L.QITT
4611	746.3889	1490.7633	1490.7617	1.07	0	(44)	0.0009	1	U	L.ITSD
4612	746.3909	1490.7672	1490.7617	3.69	0	56	6.1e-05	1	U	L.ITSD
4872	775.9730	1549.9315	1549.9304	0.71	0	(23)	0.0062	1	U	Y.RIAE
4873	517.6515	1549.9326	1549.9304	1.45	0	(23)	0.0067	1	U	Y.RIAE
4874	775.9750	1549.9354	1549.9304	3.24	0	28	0.0018	1	U	Y.RIAE
5849	884.4423	1766.8700	1766.8727	-1.54	1	(35)	0.0069	1	U	L.ITSD
5850	884.4468	1766.8790	1766.8727	3.57	1	73	1.2e-06	1	U	L.ITSD
6109	928.4966	1854.9786	1854.9799	-0.69	1	(47)	0.00029	1	U	Y.DSAK
6110	619.3339	1854.9799	1854.9799	0.02	1	(25)	0.051	1	U	Y.DSAK
6111	928.4975	1854.9804	1854.9799	0.30	1	49	0.00017	1	U	Y.DSAK
6112	619.3355	1854.9845	1854.9799	2.50	1	(31)	0.011	1	U	Y.DSAK
7028	1227.6536	2453.2926	2453.2914	0.46	0	(51)	0.00011	1	U	L.VVGA
7029	818.7722	2453.2947	2453.2914	1.31	0	(32)	0.0087	1	U	L.VVGA
7030	818.7723	2453.2952	2453.2914	1.53	0	(38)	0.0019	1	U	L.VVGA
7032	1227.6575	2453.3004	2453.2914	3.65	0	(57)	2.1e-05	1	U	L.VVGA
7033	819.0978	2454.2717	2454.2755	-1.53	0	58	2.5e-05	1	U	L.VVGA
7035	819.1023	2454.2850	2454.2755	3.91	0	(41)	0.001	1	U	L.VVGA

9. [2::sp|P0ABB0|ATPA_ECOLI](#) Mass: 55416 Score: 491 Matches: 28 (23) Sequences:
 ATP synthase subunit alpha OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=atpA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptid
129	390.2182	778.4218	778.4225	-0.92	1	30	0.01	1	U	L.KGIL
130	390.2186	778.4227	778.4225	0.27	1	(29)	0.011	1	U	L.KGIL
2117	555.2773	1108.5401	1108.5400	0.08	1	(23)	0.11	1	U	Y.DDLS
2118	555.2778	1108.5411	1108.5400	0.96	1	24	0.082	1	U	Y.DDLS
2553	578.7907	1155.5669	1155.5673	-0.34	1	21	0.11	1	U	L.AYVD
2916	402.2342	1203.6808	1203.6823	-1.22	0	(21)	0.062	1	U	F.TKGE
2918	602.8485	1203.6825	1203.6823	0.14	0	(29)	0.011	1	U	F.TKGE
2919	602.8500	1203.6855	1203.6823	2.68	0	33	0.0035	1	U	F.TKGE
3408	636.8684	1271.7223	1271.7197	1.99	0	29	0.012	1	U	L.IIGD
3409	636.8688	1271.7230	1271.7197	2.55	0	(26)	0.022	1	U	L.IIGD
3443	639.8519	1277.6892	1277.6867	1.94	2	67	2.3e-06	1	U	Y.LADV

3444	639.8522	1277.6899	1277.6867	2.51	2	(61)	9.2e-06	1	U	Y.LADV
3845	666.8425	1331.6704	1331.6681	1.72	1	52	0.00015	1	U	F.ASDL
3846	666.8435	1331.6725	1331.6681	3.29	1	(51)	0.00015	1	U	F.ASDL
4630	748.3643	1494.7140	1494.7103	2.44	1	31	0.021	1	U	L.GAPI
4631	748.3655	1494.7164	1494.7103	4.07	1	(29)	0.027	1	U	L.GAPI
5164	803.8997	1605.7849	1605.7821	1.74	1	(48)	0.00048	1	U	L.NLER
5165	803.9007	1605.7868	1605.7821	2.96	1	55	8e-05	1	U	L.NLER
5234	811.8970	1621.7795	1621.7770	1.54	1	(43)	0.0012	1	U	L.NLER
5235	811.8981	1621.7816	1621.7770	2.82	1	(43)	0.0014	1	U	L.NLER
5415	555.2819	1662.8238	1662.8213	1.48	2	(25)	0.086	1	U	F.RDRG
5416	555.2820	1662.8241	1662.8213	1.70	2	31	0.023	1	U	F.RDRG
6518	1019.9773	2037.9400	2037.9313	4.28	1	(58)	3.9e-05	1	U	L.MQEI
6553	1027.9739	2053.9332	2053.9262	3.40	1	(61)	1.4e-05	1	U	L.MQEI
6554	1027.9746	2053.9347	2053.9262	4.11	1	79	2.6e-07	1	U	L.MQEI
7068	838.7676	2513.2809	2513.2762	1.88	0	(37)	0.003	1	U	F.SAVE
7069	838.7682	2513.2829	2513.2762	2.68	0	39	0.0018	1	U	F.SAVE
7070	1257.6499	2513.2852	2513.2762	3.61	0	(30)	0.014	1	U	F.SAVE

10. [2::sp|P0A8M0|SYN ECOLI](#) Mass: 52766 Score: 303 Matches: 13(13) Sequences: 7
 Asparagine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=asnS PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
729	449.7660	897.5174	897.5172	0.31	0	32	0.003	1	U	M.SVVPV
1576	513.7482	1025.4819	1025.4818	0.11	1	24	0.059	1	U	L.ERFIE
2668	584.7786	1167.5427	1167.5408	1.65	1	(27)	0.034	1	U	L.TVSGQ
2669	584.7796	1167.5446	1167.5408	3.31	1	42	0.001	1	U	L.TVSGQ
3524	646.2997	1290.5848	1290.5840	0.60	1	(56)	3.8e-05	1	U	W.GVDLS
3525	646.3000	1290.5854	1290.5840	1.08	1	(58)	2.8e-05	1	U	W.GVDLS
3526	646.3008	1290.5871	1290.5840	2.40	1	(56)	4e-05	1	U	W.GVDLS
3527	646.3013	1290.5880	1290.5840	3.07	1	58	2.5e-05	1	U	W.GVDLS
3724	658.8455	1315.6764	1315.6772	-0.63	0	(62)	1.2e-05	1	U	F.EIQAS
3725	658.8477	1315.6808	1315.6772	2.71	0	66	5.9e-06	1	U	F.EIQAS
3895	672.7867	1343.5589	1343.5551	2.84	0	41	0.00061	1	U	L.ITASD
4959	784.3937	1566.7729	1566.7712	1.13	1	(34)	0.0085	1	U	F.KAVLE
4961	784.3960	1566.7774	1566.7712	4.01	1	41	0.002	1	U	F.KAVLE

11. [2::sp|P0A6P9|ENO ECOLI](#) Mass: 45683 Score: 282 Matches: 14(12) Sequences: 7
 Enolase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=eno PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1415	503.2715	1004.5285	1004.5291	-0.61	1	35	0.0059	1	U	Y.VLAGE
1834	538.2854	1074.5562	1074.5557	0.51	1	(33)	0.011	1	U	F.NQIGS
1835	538.2861	1074.5576	1074.5557	1.76	1	40	0.002	1	U	F.NQIGS
2040	551.3037	1100.5929	1100.5938	-0.83	0	26	0.038	1	U	Y.NGRKE
2622	581.8279	1161.6412	1161.6393	1.61	0	(55)	4.1e-05	1	U	L.AVIAE
2623	581.8284	1161.6423	1161.6393	2.55	0	68	1.7e-06	1	U	L.AVIAE
3764	660.3469	1318.6792	1318.6769	1.72	2	33	0.0089	1	U	L.GDKIQ
3766	660.3487	1318.6828	1318.6769	4.50	2	(20)	0.19	1	U	L.GDKIQ
4593	496.9412	1487.8018	1487.7983	2.35	1	(23)	0.089	1	U	L.IRIEE
4594	496.9413	1487.8021	1487.7983	2.53	1	26	0.044	1	U	L.IRIEE

6064	922.4976	1842.9806	1842.9839	-1.81	2	(40)	0.0015	1	U	Y.NQLIR
6065	922.4986	1842.9826	1842.9839	-0.68	2	54	6.7e-05	1	U	Y.NQLIR
6066	615.3353	1842.9842	1842.9839	0.14	2	(41)	0.0013	1	U	Y.NQLIR
6067	615.3369	1842.9889	1842.9839	2.71	2	(36)	0.0037	1	U	Y.NQLIR

12. [2::sp|P0A6M8|EFG ECOLI](#) Mass: 77704 Score: 276 Matches: 11(10) Sequences: 6
 Elongation factor G OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=fusA PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
160	396.2183	790.4220	790.4225	-0.60	0	(31)	0.011	1	U	F.KIATD
161	396.2185	790.4225	790.4225	0.03	0	39	0.0015	1	U	F.KIATD
2174	557.7795	1113.5445	1113.5455	-0.83	1	37	0.0029	1	U	L.QLAIG
2175	557.7811	1113.5476	1113.5455	1.91	1	(22)	0.095	1	U	L.QLAIG
2712	587.8251	1173.6356	1173.6394	-3.23	1	(37)	0.0031	1	U	F.KIATD
2713	587.8267	1173.6389	1173.6394	-0.41	1	47	0.00029	1	U	F.KIATD
4139	694.8640	1387.7135	1387.7096	2.81	0	36	0.0051	1	U	F.NVEAN
4776	765.4074	1528.8003	1528.7984	1.21	2	67	3.1e-06	1	U	Y.LGGEE
4777	765.4075	1528.8005	1528.7984	1.37	2	(65)	5.1e-06	1	U	Y.LGGEE
6331	972.4856	1942.9566	1942.9558	0.45	1	(29)	0.033	1	U	L.KDVTT
6332	972.4870	1942.9594	1942.9558	1.89	1	49	0.00028	1	U	L.KDVTT

13. [2::sp|P04805|SYE ECOLI](#) Mass: 54181 Score: 263 Matches: 12(10) Sequences: 8
 Glutamate--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=gltX PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2791	595.2964	1188.5782	1188.5775	0.61	0	(40)	0.002	1	U	F.DDQ
2792	595.2968	1188.5791	1188.5775	1.32	0	57	3.4e-05	1	U	F.DDQ
2849	598.3188	1194.6230	1194.6244	-1.18	1	35	0.0041	1	U	F.TLN
3131	411.5374	1231.5904	1231.5907	-0.23	1	31	0.014	1	U	F.TRE
3132	411.5375	1231.5906	1231.5907	-0.06	1	(24)	0.069	1	U	F.TRE
3245	625.2947	1248.5749	1248.5735	1.18	1	(36)	0.0055	1	U	L.DFI
3246	625.2955	1248.5765	1248.5735	2.44	1	38	0.0035	1	U	L.DFI
3343	631.3248	1260.6350	1260.6350	-0.01	2	25	0.067	1	U	Y.RDD
4381	719.3899	1436.7652	1436.7663	-0.78	1	27	0.027	1	U	Y.INA
5003	785.3587	1568.7028	1568.7028	0.02	1	25	0.052	1	U	Y.NAV
7314	1012.7928	3035.3565	3035.4216	-21.42	2	30	0.0093	1	U	F.VLR
7315	1012.7929	3035.3567	3035.4216	-21.36	2	(28)	0.016	1	U	F.VLR

14. [2::sp|P0AGG8|TLDD ECOLI](#) Mass: 51446 Score: 241 Matches: 9(6) Sequences: 5
 Metalloprotease TldD OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=tldD PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1264	492.7898	983.5650	983.5651	-0.10	1	27	0.011	1	U	Y.NVLIE
1346	497.2650	992.5155	992.5178	-2.31	2	(24)	0.078	1	U	F.AYADQ
1347	497.2661	992.5177	992.5178	-0.17	2	33	0.0086	1	U	F.AYADQ
4334	715.8495	1429.6844	1429.6837	0.48	2	64	7.1e-06	1	U	F.LADLD
4335	715.8503	1429.6860	1429.6837	1.58	2	(59)	2.3e-05	1	U	F.LADLD

5118	797.8970	1593.7795	1593.7787	0.48	1	98	4.5e-09	1	U	Y.APNFG
5119	797.8996	1593.7846	1593.7787	3.70	1	(88)	3.9e-08	1	U	Y.APNFG
6297	968.9833	1935.9521	1935.9499	1.14	0	22	0.16	1	U	Y.MLPKG
6298	968.9851	1935.9557	1935.9499	2.97	0	(21)	0.2	1	U	Y.MLPKG

15. [2::sp|P0A6H5|HSLU_ECOLI](#) Mass: 49677 Score: 232 Matches: 10(10) Sequences: 1
 ATP-dependent protease ATPase subunit HslU OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
440	416.2394	830.4643	830.4650	-0.82	1	(45)	0.00039	1	U	L.AKLAN
441	416.2399	830.4652	830.4650	0.21	1	50	0.00013	1	U	L.AKLAN
915	468.2816	934.5487	934.5488	-0.07	0	(31)	0.0026	1	U	F.IKVEA
916	468.2821	934.5496	934.5488	0.96	0	38	0.00042	1	U	F.IKVEA
1491	508.2871	1014.5595	1014.5597	-0.13	1	49	0.00018	1	U	L.LIEEE
1492	508.2873	1014.5600	1014.5597	0.35	1	(39)	0.0015	1	U	L.LIEEE
3912	675.8300	1349.6455	1349.6463	-0.60	2	38	0.0036	1	U	L.DALVA
3914	675.8320	1349.6495	1349.6463	2.38	2	(35)	0.0075	1	U	L.DALVA
5451	835.4315	1668.8484	1668.8471	0.74	0	(53)	9.4e-05	1	U	L.KQDAI
5452	835.4315	1668.8485	1668.8471	0.81	0	57	4.2e-05	1	U	L.KQDAI

16. [2::sp|P0C8J8|GATZ_ECOLI](#) Mass: 47535 Score: 210 Matches: 9(9) Sequences: 5
 D-tagatose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase subunit GatZ OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
444	416.7499	831.4852	831.4854	-0.28	1	31	0.0041	1	U	L.KVGP
445	416.7500	831.4854	831.4854	0.01	1	(29)	0.0059	1	U	L.KVGP
903	466.2459	930.4773	930.4770	0.25	0	(35)	0.005	1	U	F.ERIQS
904	466.2460	930.4774	930.4770	0.44	0	39	0.002	1	U	F.ERIQS
1476	507.7766	1013.5387	1013.5393	-0.61	1	41	0.00075	1	U	F.ALAQI
1477	507.7769	1013.5392	1013.5393	-0.06	1	(39)	0.0014	1	U	F.ALAQI
3075	613.8404	1225.6662	1225.6666	-0.32	0	54	3.9e-05	1	U	L.APETV
3076	613.8419	1225.6692	1225.6666	2.07	0	(40)	0.00091	1	U	L.APETV
3252	625.8052	1249.5958	1249.5939	1.55	0	45	0.00069	1	U	L.IEATS

Proteins matching a subset of these peptides:

- [2::sp|P0C8K0|KBAZ_ECOLI](#) Mass: 47562 Score: 31 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
 D-tagatose-1,6-bisphosphate aldolase subunit KbaZ OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333

17. [2::sp|P31224|ACRB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 113615 Score: 203 Matches: 7(7) Sequences: 4
 Multidrug efflux pump subunit AcrB OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=acrB
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1334	496.7743	991.5340	991.5338	0.19	0	(34)	0.0048	1	U	L.ASKLP
1336	496.7749	991.5353	991.5338	1.48	0	51	9.6e-05	1	U	L.ASKLP
2497	573.8043	1145.5940	1145.5928	1.00	0	(29)	0.025	1	U	L.GVSIN
2498	573.8046	1145.5947	1145.5928	1.65	0	42	0.0013	1	U	L.GVSIN

4049	686.3791	1370.7436	1370.7405	2.28	0	(33)	0.0077	1	U	F.KIDID
4050	686.3797	1370.7448	1370.7405	3.17	0	45	0.00046	1	U	F.KIDID
5257	814.9332	1627.8519	1627.8529	-0.61	1	65	4.6e-06	1	U	L.ATGAN

18. [2::sp|P0AFG6|ODO2_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 43984 **Score:** 184 **Matches:** 8(8) **Sequences:** 5
Dihydrolipoyllysine-residue succinyltransferase component of 2-oxoglutarate dehydrogenase
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
351	408.2649	814.5153	814.5164	-1.28	1	21	0.031	1	U	F.LVTIK
422	414.7629	827.5113	827.5116	-0.45	0	51	4e-05	1	U	Y.VKAVV
423	414.7630	827.5114	827.5116	-0.31	0	(45)	0.00014	1	U	Y.VKAVV
1325	496.2945	990.5744	990.5750	-0.54	1	32	0.0051	1	U	F.YVKAV
3091	614.3510	1226.6873	1226.6871	0.22	1	(25)	0.029	1	U	L.VTPVL
3092	614.3515	1226.6884	1226.6871	1.12	1	27	0.021	1	U	L.VTPVL
6310	970.4750	1938.9354	1938.9323	1.60	0	(35)	0.0086	1	U	L.KRYPE
6312	970.4768	1938.9389	1938.9323	3.42	0	56	5.8e-05	1	U	L.KRYPE

19. [2::sp|P30845|EPTA_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 62369 **Score:** 163 **Matches:** 7(7) **Sequences:** 4
Phosphoethanolamine transferase EptA OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=ep
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1703	526.7917	1051.5689	1051.5702	-1.21	2	22	0.052	1	U	F.ILVGA
3051	611.8067	1221.5988	1221.5990	-0.09	0	(46)	0.00059	1	U	L.IVGET
3052	611.8070	1221.5995	1221.5990	0.42	0	48	0.00032	1	U	L.IVGET
3287	627.8565	1253.6985	1253.6980	0.41	1	38	0.0012	1	U	Y.INNLQ
3288	627.8576	1253.7006	1253.6980	2.15	1	(35)	0.002	1	U	Y.INNLQ
4543	737.8992	1473.7839	1473.7827	0.80	1	58	2.8e-05	1	U	L.VKSLs
4544	737.8997	1473.7848	1473.7827	1.38	1	(33)	0.0092	1	U	L.VKSLs

20. [2::sp|P0AG67|RS1_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 61235 **Score:** 161 **Matches:** 8(7) **Sequences:** 4(4)
30S ribosomal protein S1 OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=rpsA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2451	571.7961	1141.5777	1141.5768	0.84	2	43	0.00056	1	U	L.GLKQL
2452	571.7971	1141.5797	1141.5768	2.56	2	(39)	0.0015	1	U	L.GLKQL
2935	603.8056	1205.5966	1205.5928	3.20	0	(22)	0.15	1	U	L.KSESA
2936	603.8057	1205.5968	1205.5928	3.30	0	27	0.041	1	U	L.KSESA
3159	618.7971	1235.5797	1235.5782	1.20	0	(46)	0.00057	1	U	W.NVAGE
3160	618.7976	1235.5807	1235.5782	2.00	0	51	0.00015	1	U	W.NVAGE
3537	646.8399	1291.6652	1291.6660	-0.57	1	(38)	0.0032	1	U	L.VLSVG
3539	646.8413	1291.6681	1291.6660	1.61	1	39	0.0023	1	U	L.VLSVG

21. [2::sp|P00350|6PGD_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 51563 **Score:** 158 **Matches:** 7(6) **Sequences:** 4
6-phosphogluconate dehydrogenase, decarboxylating OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=6PGD PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1015	476.2611	950.5075	950.5073	0.28	1	34	0.0038	1	U	F.LQKIT
1383	500.2423	998.4700	998.4709	-0.89	1	41	0.00078	1	U	Y.FKQIA
1384	500.2425	998.4704	998.4709	-0.47	1	(27)	0.02	1	U	Y.FKQIA
1537	511.7661	1021.5177	1021.5192	-1.53	1	30	0.018	1	U	L.ALNIE
1538	511.7669	1021.5192	1021.5192	-0.02	1	(23)	0.11	1	U	L.ALNIE
4559	739.3813	1476.7480	1476.7460	1.35	1	53	0.00011	1	U	Y.LDKGD
4560	739.3824	1476.7502	1476.7460	2.84	1	(42)	0.0013	1	U	Y.LDKGD

22. [2::sp|P08200|IDH_ECOLI](#) Mass: 46070 Score: 148 Matches: 7(7) Sequences: 4(4)
 Isocitrate dehydrogenase [NADP] OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=icd PE=
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
563	427.2850	852.5555	852.5545	1.18	0	(20)	0.012	1	U	Y.RVAIK
564	427.2854	852.5562	852.5545	2.05	0	24	0.0046	1	U	Y.RVAIK
2825	596.8328	1191.6510	1191.6499	0.88	0	(48)	0.00018	1	U	L.KVVDA
2826	596.8334	1191.6522	1191.6499	1.90	0	57	2.5e-05	1	U	L.KVVDA
3706	656.3675	1310.7204	1310.7194	0.78	0	39	0.001	1	U	Y.AGQDK
3707	656.3683	1310.7221	1310.7194	2.09	0	(36)	0.0022	1	U	Y.AGQDK
4658	751.8751	1501.7356	1501.7334	1.42	0	28	0.035	1	U	Y.IEGDG

23. [2::sp|P21599|KPYK2_ECOLI](#) Mass: 51553 Score: 138 Matches: 7(5) Sequences: 4(4)
 Pyruvate kinase II OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=pykA PE=1 SV=3
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
281	403.7243	805.4341	805.4334	0.89	1	20	0.092	1	U	F.LNIGD
3552	647.3740	1292.7335	1292.7340	-0.40	0	43	0.00028	1	U	Y.KGLPA
3553	647.3757	1292.7369	1292.7340	2.24	0	(33)	0.0023	1	U	Y.KGLPA
4207	702.3917	1402.7689	1402.7667	1.54	0	(25)	0.044	1	U	L.TEKDK
4208	702.3921	1402.7696	1402.7667	2.07	0	34	0.005	1	U	L.TEKDK
4660	752.3479	1502.6812	1502.6849	-2.40	0	(24)	0.073	1	U	F.DSAND
4661	752.3492	1502.6839	1502.6849	-0.62	0	46	0.00042	1	U	F.DSAND

24. [2::sp|P0A6F5|CH60_ECOLI](#) Mass: 57464 Score: 134 Matches: 6(6) Sequences: 3(3)
 60 kDa chaperonin OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=groL PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
5277	815.9199	1629.8253	1629.8250	0.19	1	(34)	0.0077	1	U	F.INKPE
5278	815.9201	1629.8256	1629.8250	0.41	1	36	0.0057	1	U	F.INKPE
5897	889.4544	1776.8943	1776.8934	0.49	2	(53)	0.00011	1	U	Y.FINKP
5898	889.4553	1776.8961	1776.8934	1.51	2	55	8.8e-05	1	U	Y.FINKP
6313	647.3447	1939.0124	1939.0123	0.04	1	(35)	0.0055	1	U	L.ADLRG
6314	647.3462	1939.0167	1939.0123	2.30	1	44	0.00062	1	U	L.ADLRG

25. [2::sp|P68767|AMPA_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 55358 **Score:** 124 **Matches:** 5(4) **Sequences:** 3
 Cytosol aminopeptidase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=pepA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3515	645.8068	1289.5990	1289.6000	-0.80	0	36	0.0043	1	U	L.IAASE
3518	645.8093	1289.6040	1289.6000	3.09	0	(23)	0.089	1	U	L.IAASE
4489	730.8727	1459.7309	1459.7307	0.17	2	(26)	0.052	1	U	W.RLPLG
4490	730.8755	1459.7365	1459.7307	4.02	2	37	0.0044	1	U	W.RLPLG
4796	768.3851	1534.7557	1534.7515	2.75	1	50	0.00023	1	U	L.SPIAE

26. [2::sp|P25553|ALDA_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 52411 **Score:** 118 **Matches:** 6(6) **Sequences:** 3
 Lactaldehyde dehydrogenase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=aldA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3318	629.3430	1256.6714	1256.6725	-0.88	1	36	0.004	1	U	L.VLGRG
3319	629.3439	1256.6733	1256.6725	0.67	1	(28)	0.02	1	U	L.VLGRG
3655	653.3562	1304.6978	1304.6976	0.18	0	(51)	0.00014	1	U	L.TGNTI
3656	653.3563	1304.6981	1304.6976	0.36	0	51	0.00012	1	U	L.TGNTI
5447	835.4257	1668.8369	1668.8318	3.02	0	34	0.0079	1	U	Y.EGEII
5448	835.4262	1668.8377	1668.8318	3.54	0	(32)	0.012	1	U	Y.EGEII

27. [2::sp|P0A6E4|ASSY_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 50038 **Score:** 111 **Matches:** 5(5) **Sequences:** 3
 Argininosuccinate synthase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=argG PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1390	500.7564	999.4983	999.4985	-0.25	0	32	0.0066	1	U	F.SPDDR
1391	500.7565	999.4984	999.4985	-0.07	0	(28)	0.018	1	U	F.SPDDR
4280	710.3210	1418.6274	1418.6314	-2.80	0	33	0.0063	1	U	L.TGIHN
6238	951.4656	1900.9167	1900.9126	2.16	1	46	0.00053	1	U	L.SSSAA
6239	951.4680	1900.9215	1900.9126	4.66	1	(39)	0.0024	1	U	L.SSSAA

28. [2::sp|P0AG30|RHO_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 47032 **Score:** 101 **Matches:** 6(6) **Sequences:** 2(2)
 Transcription termination factor Rho OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=rh
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1898	542.8215	1083.6285	1083.6288	-0.28	0	(33)	0.0033	1	U	Y.NTVVP
1899	542.8226	1083.6306	1083.6288	1.64	0	44	0.0003	1	U	Y.NTVVP
5874	888.4078	1774.8010	1774.7971	2.19	1	(26)	0.041	1	U	L.IDTGS
5875	888.4081	1774.8016	1774.7971	2.53	1	57	3.4e-05	1	U	L.IDTGS
5935	896.4063	1790.7981	1790.7920	3.37	1	(50)	0.00016	1	U	L.IDTGS
5936	896.4067	1790.7988	1790.7920	3.78	1	(41)	0.0012	1	U	L.IDTGS

29. [2::sp|P0A7D4|PURA_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 47543 **Score:** 98 **Matches:** 6(5) **Sequences:** 4

Adenylosuccinate synthetase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=purA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3099	614.8624	1227.7102	1227.7074	2.24	2	21	0.063	1	U	L.DVLIDG
4521	735.9212	1469.8278	1469.8202	5.21	0	25	0.032	1	U	L.RENVTV
4863	774.4020	1546.7895	1546.7913	-1.12	1	(26)	0.055	1	U	Y.QKVLD
4864	774.4040	1546.7935	1546.7913	1.48	1	28	0.038	1	U	Y.QKVLD
6591	1037.4840	2072.9535	2072.9401	6.44	2	27	0.033	1	U	W.KGVPEP
6592	1037.4840	2072.9535	2072.9401	6.44	2	(26)	0.045	1	U	W.KGVPEP

30. [2::sp|P22188|MURE_ECOLI](#) Mass: 53766 Score: 97 Matches: 5(5) Sequences: 3(3)
 UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-L-alanyl-D-glutamate--2,6-diaminopimelate ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=purA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1188	486.7773	971.5401	971.5400	0.11	2	32	0.0078	1	U	Y.LSQLNE
1189	486.7779	971.5413	971.5400	1.36	2	(29)	0.018	1	U	Y.LSQLNE
1222	488.2301	974.4457	974.4458	-0.05	0	(29)	0.014	1	U	L.VAGKGH
1223	488.2304	974.4463	974.4458	0.59	0	35	0.003	1	U	L.VAGKGH
2926	603.3191	1204.6236	1204.6200	2.99	1	29	0.022	1	U	Y.QIVGNQ

31. [2::sp|P0A8L1|SYS_ECOLI](#) Mass: 48669 Score: 96 Matches: 3(2) Sequences: 3(3)
 Serine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=serS PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1550	512.3080	1022.6015	1022.6012	0.34	1	42	0.00019	1	U	Y.ALIPT
3915	675.8554	1349.6963	1349.6980	-1.26	2	31	0.013	1	U	Y.GTGQL
4455	727.3865	1452.7585	1452.7572	0.88	0	22	0.08	1	U	Y.QQADG

32. [2::sp|P76403|YEQQ_ECOLI](#) Mass: 51446 Score: 94 Matches: 5(4) Sequences: 3(3)
 Uncharacterized protease YegQ OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=yegQ PE=3 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1146	483.7359	965.4573	965.4567	0.67	0	21	0.15	1	U	Y.SVSDR
3871	669.8053	1337.5960	1337.5921	2.93	0	(43)	0.0009	1	U	F.MIEEA
3872	669.8054	1337.5963	1337.5921	3.11	0	46	0.00049	1	U	F.MIEEA
3979	453.9167	1358.7283	1358.7306	-1.68	0	27	0.033	1	U	Y.RKAID
3980	453.9172	1358.7297	1358.7306	-0.67	0	(26)	0.041	1	U	Y.RKAID

33. [2::sp|P76658|HLDE_ECOLI](#) Mass: 51247 Score: 91 Matches: 4(4) Sequences: 2(2)
 Bifunctional protein HldE OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=hldE PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
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3019	608.8250	1215.6355	1215.6347	0.62	0	39	0.0024	1	U	Y.DVTGA
3020	608.8254	1215.6363	1215.6347	1.32	0	(30)	0.019	1	U	Y.DVTGA
4283	710.3580	1418.7014	1418.7042	-1.96	1	52	0.00014	1	U	W.VVSFE
4284	710.3605	1418.7065	1418.7042	1.65	1	(42)	0.0016	1	U	W.VVSFE

34. [1::sp|cRAP054|P04264|K2C1_HUMAN](#) Mass: 66170 Score: 90 Matches: 4(3) Sequences: 3
 Keratin, type II cytoskeletal 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=KRT1 PE=1 SV=6
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2954	604.8307	1207.6468	1207.6449	1.64	0	27	0.025	1	U	F.VTIKK
3438	639.3213	1276.6280	1276.6259	1.68	1	21	0.18	2	U	L.KSDQS
4690	757.7994	1513.5842	1513.5819	1.55	1	(33)	0.0011	1	U	Y.GSGGG
4691	757.8008	1513.5871	1513.5819	3.48	1	43	0.00013	1	U	Y.GSGGG

35. [2::sp|P0A825|GLYA_ECOLI](#) Mass: 45459 Score: 90 Matches: 6(4) Sequences: 3
 Serine hydroxymethyltransferase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=glyA PE=1 SV=6
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1594	514.8032	1027.5918	1027.5914	0.40	2	30	0.0098	1	U	F.LVDLVD
1595	514.8039	1027.5932	1027.5914	1.82	2	(28)	0.014	1	U	F.LVDLVD
2747	590.3163	1178.6180	1178.6183	-0.22	2	32	0.0094	1	U	L.ILAKGG
2748	590.3175	1178.6204	1178.6183	1.85	2	(23)	0.088	1	U	L.ILAKGG
3414	637.3312	1272.6479	1272.6463	1.30	1	(25)	0.072	1	U	Y.KVVS GG
3415	637.3317	1272.6488	1272.6463	1.98	1	27	0.039	1	U	Y.KVVS GG

36. [2::sp|P21507|SRMB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 49998 Score: 88 Matches: 4(4) Sequences: 2
 ATP-dependent RNA helicase SrmB OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=srmB PE=1 SV=6
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
792	454.2294	906.4442	906.4447	-0.48	1	(27)	0.038	1	U	L.EALQDK
793	454.2294	906.4442	906.4447	-0.48	1	34	0.0066	1	U	L.EALQDK
2759	591.2935	1180.5725	1180.5724	0.06	0	53	0.0001	1	U	L.GSAPTG
2760	591.2939	1180.5732	1180.5724	0.67	0	(29)	0.024	1	U	L.GSAPTG

37. [1::sp|cRAP087|P02769|ALBU_BOVIN](#) Mass: 71244 Score: 78 Matches: 3(3) Sequences: 3
 Serum albumin OS=Bos taurus GN=ALB PE=1 SV=4
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2753	590.8274	1179.6403	1179.6400	0.27	2	55	3e-05	1	U	Y.GFQNA
2754	590.8291	1179.6436	1179.6400	3.07	2	(53)	4.3e-05	1	U	Y.GFQNA
5078	792.4566	1582.8986	1582.8930	3.55	2	22	0.039	1	U	F.AVEGP

38. [2::sp|P27306|STHA_ECOLI](#) Mass: 51984 Score: 78 Matches: 3(3) Sequences: 2
 Soluble pyridine nucleotide transhydrogenase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
5195	807.9261	1613.8376	1613.8373	0.22	2	37	0.0036	1	U	L.ALQNI
5267	815.4388	1628.8631	1628.8621	0.63	0	(37)	0.0035	1	U	Y.TIPEIS
5268	815.4392	1628.8639	1628.8621	1.08	0	40	0.0015	1	U	Y.TIPEIS

39. [2::sp|P02931|OMPF_ECOLI](#) Mass: 39309 Score: 70 Matches: 4(4) Sequences: 2
 Outer membrane protein F OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=ompF PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3404	636.8448	1271.6750	1271.6721	2.30	0	43	0.00091	1	U	Y.IINQI
3405	636.8456	1271.6766	1271.6721	3.54	0	(30)	0.016	1	U	Y.IINQI
4575	742.3797	1482.7448	1482.7426	1.49	1	27	0.031	1	U	Y.GAADR
4576	742.3798	1482.7451	1482.7426	1.65	1	(27)	0.035	1	U	Y.GAADR

40. [2::sp|P21888|SYC_ECOLI](#) Mass: 52454 Score: 68 Matches: 3(3) Sequences: 2
 Cysteine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=cysS PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2349	566.7798	1131.5450	1131.5448	0.21	2	27	0.031	1	U	L.GLLEQE
4549	738.8760	1475.7374	1475.7369	0.37	0	(30)	0.025	1	U	L.RGTDKT
4550	738.8777	1475.7408	1475.7369	2.69	0	41	0.0019	1	U	L.RGTDKT

41. [1::sp|cRAP112|P00761|TRYP_PIG](#) Mass: 25078 Score: 63 Matches: 3(3) Sequences: 1
 Trypsin OS=Sus scrofa PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
892	465.2874	928.5603	928.5593	1.12	1	26	0.016	1	U	L.IKLSSP
3316	629.3329	1256.6513	1256.6513	0.02	1	38	0.0025	1	U	Y.VNWIQQ
3317	629.3345	1256.6545	1256.6513	2.54	1	(33)	0.0077	1	U	Y.VNWIQQ

42. [1::sp|cRAP039|P13645|K1C10_HUMAN](#) Mass: 59020 Score: 62 Matches: 4(2) Sequences: 1
 Keratin, type I cytoskeletal 10 OS=Homo sapiens GN=KRT10 PE=1 SV=6
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
372	410.2275	818.4405	818.4385	2.38	0	20	0.17	1	U	Y.KSEITE
3932	677.7684	1353.5222	1353.5182	2.96	0	22	0.015	1	U	Y.GGGSSS
3933	677.7684	1353.5223	1353.5182	3.04	0	(21)	0.02	1	U	Y.GGGSSS
5527	843.4578	1684.9011	1684.8995	0.93	2	22	0.1	1	U	L.KNQILN

43. [2::sp|P24182|ACCC_ECOLI](#) Mass: 49745 Score: 52 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
Biotin carboxylase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=accC PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1535	511.7482	1021.4818	1021.4829	-1.05	0	(49)	0.00026	1	U	F.AEQVE
1536	511.7486	1021.4827	1021.4829	-0.15	0	54	8.4e-05	1	U	F.AEQVE

44. [2::sp|P0AEI1|MIAB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 53971 Score: 51 Matches: 3(1) Sequences: 2
tRNA-2-methylthio-N(6)-dimethylallyladenosine synthase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=accC PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2129	555.7608	1109.5070	1109.5063	0.66	0	31	0.013	1	U	F.EGTPDM
2130	555.7608	1109.5070	1109.5063	0.66	0	(21)	0.11	1	U	F.EGTPDM
2695	586.3290	1170.6435	1170.6244	16.3	1	20	0.12	2	U	L.AAQGVR

45. [2::sp|P0A6H1|CLPX_ECOLI](#) Mass: 46726 Score: 50 Matches: 3(2) Sequences: 2
ATP-dependent Clp protease ATP-binding subunit ClpX OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=accC PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1178	486.2987	970.5827	970.5811	1.70	1	22	0.028	1	U	L.RSIVEA
3503	644.8446	1287.6746	1287.6711	2.79	1	(24)	0.092	1	U	L.AQVEPE
3504	644.8453	1287.6761	1287.6711	3.94	1	28	0.034	1	U	L.AQVEPE

46. [2::sp|P31979|NUOF_ECOLI](#) Mass: 49774 Score: 48 Matches: 3(1) Sequences: 2
NADH-quinone oxidoreductase subunit F OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=accC PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1708	527.2711	1052.5277	1052.5291	-1.33	2	(23)	0.077	1	U	L.VRNLEE
1709	527.2721	1052.5296	1052.5291	0.52	2	29	0.022	1	U	L.VRNLEE
4686	757.3712	1512.7279	1512.7209	4.63	2	24	0.065	1	U	W.QPGGAG

47. [2::sp|P16869|FHUE_ECOLI](#) Mass: 81239 Score: 47 Matches: 3(1) Sequences: 2
FhuE receptor OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=fhuE PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1755	530.2936	1058.5727	1058.5682	4.31	1	27	0.034	1	U	Y.QAITK
1756	530.2941	1058.5737	1058.5682	5.24	1	(21)	0.13	2	U	Y.QAITK
1945	544.8006	1087.5866	1087.5985	-10.94	0	21	0.16	1	U	W.NSGKR

48. [2::sp|P17445|BETB_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 53163 **Score:** 45 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 1(1)
NAD/NADP-dependent betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=aspA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4090	689.3677	1376.7208	1376.7122	6.26	1	45	0.00052	1	U	W.KSAPA
4091	689.3682	1376.7218	1376.7122	6.96	1	(34)	0.0065	1	U	W.KSAPA

49. [2::sp|P0AC38|ASPA_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 52950 **Score:** 45 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 1(1)
Aspartate ammonia-lyase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=aspA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3717	658.3463	1314.6779	1314.6779	0.03	1	45	0.00054	1	U	M.SNNIR
3718	658.3475	1314.6804	1314.6779	1.89	1	(28)	0.025	1	U	M.SNNIR

50. [2::sp|P60906|SYH_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 47285 **Score:** 41 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 1(1)
Histidine--tRNA ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=hisS PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4626	747.9306	1493.8466	1493.8453	0.89	0	(33)	0.0027	1	U	Y.SEIRL
4627	747.9321	1493.8497	1493.8453	2.94	0	41	0.00046	1	U	Y.SEIRL

51. [2::sp|P77748|YDIJ_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 114259 **Score:** 40 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 2(2)
Uncharacterized protein YdiJ OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=ydiJ PE=4 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3874	669.8725	1337.7304	1337.7013	21.8	0	22	0.051	1	U	L.SEKHIG
4445	726.4171	1450.8195	1450.7854	23.6	1	21	0.038	1	U	L.SEKHIG

52. [2::sp|P02943|LAMB_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 49995 **Score:** 40 **Matches:** 1(1) **Sequences:** 1(1)
Maltoporin OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=lamB PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2978	606.2841	1210.5536	1210.5500	2.97	0	40	0.0017	1	U	Y.ATDSMT

53. [2::sp|P05793|ILVC_ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 54376 **Score:** 37 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 1(1)
Ketol-acid reductoisomerase (NADP(+)) OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=i
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
6194	944.9369	1887.8592	1887.8526	3.49	2	40	0.0018	1	U	F.ETAPQY

[6195](#) 944.9377 1887.8609 1887.8526 4.39 2 (32) 0.0099 1 U F.ETAPQY

54. [2::sp|P0AD61|KPYK1 ECOLI](#) Mass: 51039 Score: 36 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
Pyruvate kinase I OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=pykF PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
6029	915.9451	1829.8756	1829.8717	2.12	0	36	0.0051	1	U	F.TTDKSV
6030	915.9452	1829.8758	1829.8717	2.25	0	(33)	0.0097	1	U	F.TTDKSV

55. [2::sp|P31068|FLIH ECOLI](#) Mass: 25149 Score: 34 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
Flagellar assembly protein FliH OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=fliH PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
628	436.2719	870.5293	870.5174	13.6	0	(27)	0.0091	1	U	L.IKQIQQL
629	436.2720	870.5295	870.5174	13.9	0	34	0.0016	1	U	L.IKQIQQL

56. [2::sp|P0A9J8|PHEA ECOLI](#) Mass: 43312 Score: 34 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
P-protein OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=pheA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4535	736.9085	1471.8025	1471.7704	21.8	2	(33)	0.0069	1	U	L.LMATGQ
4536	736.9094	1471.8042	1471.7704	22.9	2	36	0.0034	1	U	L.LMATGQ

57. [2::sp|P33224|AIDB ECOLI](#) Mass: 61235 Score: 33 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1
Putative acyl-CoA dehydrogenase AidB OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=aidB PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2482	572.8206	1143.6267	1143.5996	23.7	0	33	0.0068	1	U	W.DRRADA

58. [2::sp|P0A953|FABB ECOLI](#) Mass: 42928 Score: 32 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
3-oxoacyl-[acyl-carrier-protein] synthase 1 OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=fabB PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3519	645.8331	1289.6516	1289.6463	4.10	0	32	0.014	1	U	L.NIVTET
3520	645.8359	1289.6573	1289.6463	8.55	0	(27)	0.048	1	U	L.NIVTET

59. [2::sp|P0AB89|PUR8 ECOLI](#) Mass: 51625 Score: 31 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1
Adenylosuccinate lyase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=purB PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
11	380.2434	758.4723	758.4538	24.5	1	(22)	0.038	2	U	Y.EK L KEL.T
12	380.2436	758.4726	758.4538	24.8	1	31	0.0046	1	U	Y.EK L KEL.T

60. [2::sp|P25888|RHLE ECOLI](#) Mass: 50016 Score: 31 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1(1)
 ATP-dependent RNA helicase RhIE OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=rhIE PE=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3150	618.3060	1234.5975	1234.5942	2.69	0	31	0.019	1	U	L.AAQIGE
3151	618.3060	1234.5975	1234.5942	2.69	0	(28)	0.04	1	U	L.AAQIGE

61. [2::sp|P0A817|METK ECOLI](#) Mass: 42153 Score: 30 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 S-adenosylmethionine synthase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=metK PE=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
5148	802.9318	1603.8491	1603.8457	2.08	1	30	0.019	1	U	F.QYDDGK

62. [2::sp|P08722|PTV3B ECOLI](#) Mass: 66896 Score: 29 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 PTS system beta-glucoside-specific EIIBCA component OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12)
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3636	651.8489	1301.6832	1301.6723	8.38	1	29	0.022	1	U	L.LMPAIM

63. [2::sp|P09099|XYLB ECOLI](#) Mass: 52927 Score: 29 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 Xylulose kinase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=xylB PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4085	688.8568	1375.6989	1375.6765	16.3	1	29	0.028	1	U	W.RQMLAD

64. [2::sp|P0A9B2|G3P1 ECOLI](#) Mass: 35681 Score: 29 Matches: 2(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase A OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3240	624.8162	1247.6178	1247.6146	2.54	1	(22)	0.14	1	U	F.DAKAGI
3241	624.8168	1247.6191	1247.6146	3.62	1	29	0.031	1	U	F.DAKAGI

65. [2::sp|P28912|YHHI ECOLI](#) Mass: 43574 Score: 29 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1(1)

H repeat-associated putative transposase YhhI OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
897	465.7670	929.5195	929.5294	-10.66	0	29	0.019	1	U	F.AVKGTQG
898	465.7673	929.5200	929.5294	-10.15	0	(27)	0.029	1	U	F.AVKGTQG

66. [2::sp|P24175|MANB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 50716 Score: 29 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1(1)
 Phosphomannomutase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=manB PE=3 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2029	550.7999	1099.5852	1099.5947	-8.66	1	29	0.019	1	U	Y.INVKNL
2030	550.8004	1099.5863	1099.5947	-7.66	1	(25)	0.046	1	U	Y.INVKNL

67. [2::sp|P25552|GPPA_ECOLI](#) Mass: 55293 Score: 28 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 Guanosine-5'-triphosphate,3'-diphosphate pyrophosphatase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=gppA PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3500	644.8319	1287.6491	1287.6459	2.53	0	31	0.017	1	U	L.GKEIIA

68. [2::sp|P37652|BCSB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 86140 Score: 27 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 Cyclic di-GMP-binding protein OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=bcsB PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3416	637.3353	1272.6561	1272.6384	14.0	0	27	0.037	1	U	L.QAAKGI

69. [2::sp|P30863|DKGB_ECOLI](#) Mass: 29475 Score: 27 Matches: 2(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 2,5-diketo-D-gluconic acid reductase B OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=dkgB PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
517	423.2576	844.5007	844.5018	-1.28	1	(21)	0.075	1	U	L.KESLQKL
518	423.2582	844.5019	844.5018	0.17	1	27	0.014	1	U	L.KESLQKL

70. [2::sp|P77171|YDCI_ECOLI](#) Mass: 33552 Score: 27 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1(1)
 Uncharacterized HTH-type transcriptional regulator YdcI OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=833333 GN=ydcI PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1486	508.2567	1014.4988	1014.5206	-21.51	0	(26)	0.029	1	U	F.ERGRQ
1487	508.2568	1014.4991	1014.5206	-21.25	0	27	0.023	1	U	F.ERGRQ

71. [2::sp|P28305|PABC ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 30266 **Score:** 27 **Matches:** 1(1) **Sequences:** 1
Aminodeoxychorismate lyase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=pabC PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
264	401.7186	801.4226	801.4344	-14.80	0	27	0.028	1	U	L.RNEGITL

72. [2::sp|P0AEI4|RIMO ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 50064 **Score:** 27 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 1
Ribosomal protein S12 methylthiotransferase RimO OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=rpoD PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2769	591.8585	1181.7025	1181.7020	0.44	2	(24)	0.012	1	U	F.LSLVPE
2770	591.8594	1181.7042	1181.7020	1.90	2	27	0.0063	1	U	F.LSLVPE

73. [2::sp|P77335|HLYE ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 33852 **Score:** 27 **Matches:** 1(1) **Sequences:** 1
Hemolysin E, chromosomal OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=hlyE PE=1 SV=4
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4352	716.8865	1431.7584	1431.7391	13.5	0	27	0.04	1	U	Y.NEKKAS

74. [2::sp|P00963|ASNA ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 36742 **Score:** 26 **Matches:** 1(1) **Sequences:** 1
Aspartate--ammonia ligase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=asnA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2604	581.2923	1160.5700	1160.5422	24.0	0	26	0.051	1	U	L.SRVGDG

75. [2::sp|P63020|NFUA ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 21212 **Score:** 26 **Matches:** 2(2) **Sequences:** 1
Fe/S biogenesis protein NfuA OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=nfuA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1746	529.7956	1057.5766	1057.6019	-23.88	1	26	0.035	1	U	L.KEGIE
1747	529.7961	1057.5777	1057.6019	-22.84	1	(25)	0.051	1	U	L.KEGIE

76. [2::sp|P45420|YHCD ECOLI](#) **Mass:** 86465 **Score:** 26 **Matches:** 2(1) **Sequences:** 1
Uncharacterized outer membrane usher protein YhcD OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=yhcD PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1539	511.7671	1021.5197	1021.5374	-17.34	2	26	0.05	1	U	-.MLKKT
1540	511.7679	1021.5211	1021.5374	-15.91	2	(23)	0.095	1	U	-.MLKKT

77. [1::sp|cRAP008|P00722|BGAL ECOLI](#) Mass: 117321 Score: 25 Matches: 1(0) Sequences: 1(0)
Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) GN=lacZ PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2370	568.2722	1134.5299	1134.5305	-0.58	0	25	0.056	1	U	Y.GQDSRL

Proteins matching the same set of peptides:

[2::sp|P00722|BGAL ECOLI](#) Mass: 117321 Score: 25 Matches: 1(0) Sequences: 1(0)
Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=lacZ PE=1 SV=2

78. [2::sp|P76655|YQIG ECOLI](#) Mass: 92021 Score: 25 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
Putative outer membrane usher protein YqiG OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
388	412.7111	823.4076	823.4076	0.06	2	28	0.024	1	U	L.NSLGSLSF

79. [2::sp|P0ABF6|CDD ECOLI](#) Mass: 31805 Score: 25 Matches: 2(2) Sequences: 1(1)
Cytidine deaminase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=cdd PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
626	436.2469	870.4792	870.4698	10.7	1	(24)	0.023	1	U	L.QSALEPIL
627	436.2474	870.4803	870.4698	12.1	1	25	0.02	1	U	L.QSALEPIL

80. [2::sp|P0A6A3|ACKA ECOLI](#) Mass: 43605 Score: 25 Matches: 2(1) Sequences: 1(1)
Acetate kinase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=ackA PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1187	486.7771	971.5397	971.5400	-0.28	0	25	0.039	1	U	L.VIAQDASR
1196	487.2679	972.5212	972.5240	-2.86	0	(21)	0.13	1	U	L.VIAQDASR

81. [2::sp|P17115|GUTQ ECOLI](#) Mass: 34181 Score: 24 Matches: 2(1) Sequences: 1(1)
Arabinose 5-phosphate isomerase GutQ OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=gu
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
987	473.2758	944.5370	944.5291	8.35	2	(22)	0.079	1	U	L.ELSRTGLG
988	473.2764	944.5382	944.5291	9.64	2	24	0.041	1	U	L.ELSRTGLG

82. [2::sp|P0A915|OMPW ECOLI](#) Mass: 22913 Score: 24 Matches: 1(0) Sequences: 1(0)
 Outer membrane protein W OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=ompW PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2404	570.2636	1138.5127	1138.5142	-1.38	1	24	0.064	1	U	L.GGFSVTV

83. [2::sp|P25744|MDTG ECOLI](#) Mass: 44067 Score: 24 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 Multidrug resistance protein MdtG OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=mdtG PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1882	541.3386	1080.6627	1080.6543	7.76	2	24	0.005	1	U	Y.VQTPLQ

84. [2::sp|P77416|HYFD ECOLI](#) Mass: 51949 Score: 24 Matches: 1(0) Sequences: 1(0)
 Hydrogenase-4 component D OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=hyfD PE=3 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2507	574.8048	1147.5949	1147.6125	-15.30	2	24	0.071	1	U	L.TLVNV

85. [2::sp|P37909|YBGD ECOLI](#) Mass: 19940 Score: 24 Matches: 1(1) Sequences: 1(1)
 Uncharacterized fimbrial-like protein YbgD OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=ybgD PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1508	509.2959	1016.5773	1016.5688	8.34	1	24	0.046	1	U	F.KGQKTL

86. [2::sp|P08839|PT1 ECOLI](#) Mass: 63750 Score: 24 Matches: 2(0) Sequences: 1(0)
 Phosphoenolpyruvate-protein phosphotransferase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=pt1 PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
6202	630.6514	1888.9325	1888.9425	-5.32	0	(20)	0.25	1	U	F.ITDAGG
6203	630.6514	1888.9325	1888.9425	-5.32	0	24	0.098	1	U	F.ITDAGG

Search Parameters

Type of search : MS/MS Ion Search
 Enzyme : Chymotrypsin
 Fixed modifications : [Carbamidomethyl \(C\)](#)
 Variable modifications : [Deamidated \(NQ\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link \(K\)](#), [Oxidation \(M\)](#)
 Mass values : Monoisotopic

Protein Mass : Unrestricted
Peptide Mass Tolerance : $\pm$ 25 ppm
Fragment Mass Tolerance: $\pm$ 0.8 Da
Max Missed Cleavages : 2
Instrument type : ESI-TRAP
Number of queries : 7342

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>